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SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

D9.1. Polish River Pilot Specification and Baseline measurements

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1. Executive Summary

The "Polish RP Specification and Baseline Measurements" deliverable within the framework of the CRISTAL project presents a detailed analysis of the Inland Waterways Transport (IWT) market in Poland. This document aims to provide a thorough overview of the current state of the IWT market while identifying potential market segments for integration into contemporary supply chains. The results of the study pointed to years of neglect in the area of inland fleets and the infrastructure needed to develop and implement inland shipping into modern supply chains.

Despite the neglect, the implementation of inland shipping into supply chains in Poland is still possible. As part of the report, a set of factors influencing the feasibility of implementing IWW into supply chains was developed. Among the factors identified: the value of the cargo, the characteristics of the cargo, and its type, incoterms conditions, and the frequency of cargo shipment.

Based on desk research, a concept was built for the implementation of four pilot cruises aimed at studying the practical aspects of IWW implementation in supply chains. As a tool to support the development of IWW in the pilots, a smart buoy project will be developed to allow stakeholders to track shipping conditions in real time. The buoy will make it possible to study parameters such as water level and temperature, seeps under bridges, and traffic in the shipping lane. A side goal of the implemented pilots is to study public awareness of IWT and increase interest in IWT in the transportation and logistics industry.

Scheduled for Q3 of 2024, three trips on the Vistula River and one on the Oder River and the international shipping lane to Antwerp are related to the transport of three types of cargo: bulk cargo in the Port of Gdansk-Plock relation, conventional general cargo from Wloclawek to the Port of Gdansk, and containerized cargo in the same relation.

In order to comprehensively study the effects of conducting the pilots, the project consortium has developed a set of performance indicators that will be measured during the implementation of the voyage. The indicators were divided into three areas - economic, environmental and social. Based on the declarations of the selected cruise operator and cargo gestors, a baseline level was created for all performance indicators.

In conclusion, this report underscores the potential of IWT to contribute to a more sustainable and efficient transport infrastructure in Poland. With targeted investments and strategic initiatives, IWT can become a cornerstone of the country's logistics framework, supporting both economic growth and environmental sustainability.

1.1. Introduction

The primary objective of this report is to present a comprehensive overview of the Inland Waterways Transport (IWT) market in Poland and to identify potential market segments suitable for integration into supply chains. The pilot containerized barge voyage conducted in 2021 as part of the Emma-Extension project highlighted concerns from various regional industries regarding the future development of IWT. This paper aims to address these concerns by providing an extensive market analysis of available equipment and identifying potential locations for the development of reloading quays and future ports. Additionally, the report offers an in-depth examination of the supply side, highlighting numerous factors that affect the suitability of supply chains for the implementation of IWT within the current infrastructure and market conditions. Furthermore, this deliverable outlines a detailed concept and description of pilot river voyages to be conducted under the CRISTAL project framework.

The main objective of the pilots carried out within the framework of the project is to identify opportunities for the implementation of IWT and increase its share in modern supply chains, which corresponds to the overall objectives of the Cristal project. Due to the extreme navigational conditions within the location of the pilot, smart buoys developed by L-PIT will be a tool to support the prediction of navigational conditions and improve the transparency of the supply chain. The outcome of the pilots will be a set of tools and good practices for those responsible for creating supply chains, and a set of recommendations for the industry and authorities to improve navigational conditions and thus stakeholders' propensity to implement IWW. The pilots will be complemented by a set of social surveys verifying IWT awareness among the public and businesses.

1.2. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This report is systematically organized into four main chapters:

- The first chapter provides an overview of the Inland Waterways Transport (IWT) market in Poland, encompassing both supply and demand side analyses. The supply side research includes a detailed examination of the available fleet and operators, as well as the availability of terminals and infrastructure. The conclusions drawn from the limited infrastructure availability have led to the development of multi-use IWT wharfs concepts and supply chain model that can operate with constrained infrastructure.
- The second chapter focuses on the demand side analysis, identifying current cargo flows through Polish IWT and modelling potential developments in cargo volumes suitable for IWT operations.
- The third chapter outlines various factors influencing the adaptation of supply chains to IWT operations, including cargo type and characteristics, Incoterms, cargo frequency, and the distance between loading/delivery locations and the nearest IWT wharf.
- The fourth chapter presents a detailed concept of the river pilot projects scheduled under the CRISTAL project framework. This concept encompasses selected cargo groups, chosen technologies, and the geographical coverage of the scheduled pilots.

2. IWW Transport market in Poland

2.1. IWW operators market

Until 1990, the inland waterway transport (IWT) market in Poland was predominantly comprised of state-owned enterprises. These enterprises operated within strictly defined regions, a structure influenced by navigational conditions and designed to prevent intra-industry competition. During this period, the most significant players in the cargo transportation market were:

- PP "Żegluga na Odrze" (headquartered in Wrocław), which controlled 65% of Poland's total cargo transportation fleet
- PP "Żegluga Bydgoska" (headquartered in Bydgoszcz), which managed 15% of the state's cargo-carrying fleet.

PP "Żegluga na Odrze" operated along the Odra (Oder) Waterway, encompassing the Odra River, the Gliwice Canal, and the Kędzierzyn Canal. In contrast, PP "Żegluga Bydgoska" operated on the lower Vistula River, the Vistula-Oder waterway (Brda-Bydgoszcz Canal-Noteć-Warta), the Warta from Poznań to Ujście, and the lower Oder. This regional fragmentation persists today, with operators primarily divided into two main inland corridors: the Odra and Vistula rivers.

Post-1990, economic transformations and the liberalization of access to the carrier profession initiated significant changes in the structure of the IWT market in Poland. Capital-strong companies entered the privatization process, while some state-owned enterprises went bankrupt, leading to the establishment of new private companies based on their assets.

Over the past 25 years, there has been a clear trend towards decreasing company size in terms of employee numbers among Polish IWT operators. In 2010, the average shipping company employed 8.1 persons; by 2015, this number had decreased to 4.5, and by 2021, the average employment further declined to 3.6 employees. Consequently, the entity structure of the inland shipping market in Poland, mirroring trends in other EU countries, is characterized by high fragmentation.

Table 1 Number of IWT companies in Poland between 1995-2021

Year	Number of entities		Total employed persons	Average employees per entity
	Total	With one vessel		
1995	13	2	:	:
2000	22	5	:	:
2005	64	19	:	:
2010	83	36	670	8,1
2011	81	38	616	7,6
2012	86	37	487	5,7
2013	67	:	465	6,9
2014	85	:	425	5,0
2015	96	:	435	4,5
2016	110	:	483	4,4
2017	101	:	457	4,5
2018	117	:	488	4,2

2019	115	:	498	4,3
2020	111	:	406	3,7
2021	109	:	388	3,6

Source: Eurostat

The multi-ship shipping companies that originated from former state-owned enterprises have largely lost their significance in cargo transportation. Currently, only a few companies qualify as multi-vessel operators. The remaining IWT companies typically operate one or a few vessels, primarily focusing on the Oder River in the Szczecin region and the Upper Channelized Oder. Other companies have shifted their operations towards international shipping in Germany or the Netherlands or have redirected their assets towards tourism services.

Table 2 Selected multi-vessel IWT companies in Poland

Company	Geographical coverage	Fleet	Market segment
NAVIGAR TRANS Sp z o.o.	Germany, Lower Oder,	- 9 pushers, - 18 barges 400 - 1000 tons, - 3 motor barges 700 – 900 tons, - 5 pontoons (300 tons).	Preferred cargo: - project cargo, - bulk – coal, aggregates, fertilizers, grain, scrap - general cargo (steel).
Fabico Group	Germany, Lower Oder,	- 12 pushers, - 10 barges 550-1300tons - 3 barges 350 tons, - 3 pontoons (200 tons).	Preferred cargo: - project cargo, - bulk – coal, aggregates, fertilizers, grain, scrap
TRANS-WOD Błocki Czesław	Seaport Gdansk, Lower Vistula	- 2 pushers, - 4 barges 370-800tons	Preferred cargo: - project cargo, yachts
„Żegluga Płocka Mariusz Pielaciński”	Lower Vistula	- 10 pushers - 30 barges	Preferred cargo: - project cargo

Source: Own elaboration

Remaining IWT companies have one or couple of vessels at their disposal. Their main area of operation is currently the Oder River in the Szczecin region and the Upper Channelized Oder. Other companies are focusing their business on international shipping in Germany or Netherlands, alternatively their shifted their assets towards touristic services.

2.2. Available fleet

In the 1970s, Poland's inland waterway transport (IWT) operators managed a modern cargo fleet, a result of significant modernization efforts in the 1960s. This modernization introduced self-propelled barges and a push barge system, replacing the older barge towing method. However, fleet development stalled after 1980 due to reduced investment in IWW fleet and the privatization process. The most significant fleet decline occurred between 1990 and 2000, with the number and tonnage of motor barges decreasing over threefold and the number of non-powered barges (pushed and towed) decreasing by 2.6-fold and their tonnage by 2.2-fold.

Table 3 Polish IWT fleet by number and load capacity

Years	Self-propelled barge		Dumb and pushed vessel	
	Number	Thousand tonnes	Number	Thousand tonnes
1980	331	154,0	1239	535,0
1985	328	152,0	1155	517,0
1990	319	147,6	1018	470,9
1995	172	81,0	565	271,0
2000	105	49,0	387	205,0
2001	98	45,9	500	235,9
2002	92	43,4	490	229,8
2003	95	45,5	495	:
2004	93	45,5	494	237,4
2005	95	50,0	479	233,0
2006	98	56,0	471	231,0
2007	107	64,6	431	217,7
2008	109	68,0	431	213,0
2009	104	65,0	508	236,0
2010	79	55,3	518	240,8
2011	67	46,0	484	228,8
2012	71	51,8	477	223,2
2013	71	53,5	500	233,8
2014	79	56,1	504	235,9
2015	89	66,9	511	236,6
2016	91	68,1	516	235,5
2017	89	65,6	509	234,3
2018	89	66,8	462	210,9
2019	80	62,0	402	183,0
2020	69	53,9	182	80,6
2021	71	55,8	174	76,1

Source: Eurostat, GUS

Despite the fleet reduction, only 40% of the shipping potential was utilized during this period, leading to a continued downward trend in fleet supply, except for self-propelled barges. Between 2000 and 2021, the tonnage of self-propelled barges increased from 49,000 tons to 55,800 tons.

The Polish barge fleet primarily consists of non-self-propelled barges, with the BP-500 and BP-600 push barges being the most prevalent, each with capacities of 488 and 580 tons, respectively, and a draft of 1.6 meters. These vessels typically operate in sets with pushers, such as the "Łoś," "Żubr," "Bizon," and "Muflon," alongside up to two push barges. However, there is a growing trend towards increasing the share of self-propelled barges in the fleet. By 2021, self-propelled barges accounted for 29% of the total number of barges and 42.3% of the tonnage. The average capacity of a self-propelled barge in Poland rose to 785.9 tons in 2021, from 700 tons in 2010 and 466.7 tons in 2000. Notably, 31% of these barges fall within the 1,000 to 1,499-ton range, while no self-propelled barges exceed 1,500 tons.

The average size of unpowered barges has remained stable since 1980, with an average capacity of 437.4 tons in 2021. This category is dominated by barges up to 249 tons (35.1% in 2021) and those up to 399 tons (64.4% of the total pushed and towed fleet). The versatile nature of Poland's fleet allows it to transport a

variety of **dry bulk goods**, such as coal, steel, fertilizers, grain, sand, gravel, and cement, as well as **oversized cargo**. Push barges in Poland can transport loads up to 37 meters long, 7 meters wide, and 5.5 meters high, while pontoon sets can handle cargoes up to 77 meters long, 9 meters wide, and 4.5 meters high.

Table 4 Average tonnage of barges in Poland, by type

Years	Self-propelled barge	Dumb and pushed vessel	Years	Self-propelled barge	Dumb and pushed vessel
1980	465,3	431,8	2009	625,0	464,6
1985	463,4	447,6	2010	700,0	464,9
1990	462,7	462,6	2011	686,6	472,7
1995	470,9	479,6	2012	729,6	467,9
2000	466,7	529,7	2013	753,5	467,6
2001	468,4	471,8	2014	710,1	468,1
2002	471,7	469,0	2015	751,7	463,0
2003	478,9	n/a	2016	748,4	456,4
2004	489,2	480,6	2017	737,1	460,3
2005	526,3	486,4	2018	750,6	456,5
2006	571,4	490,4	2019	775,0	455,2
2007	603,7	505,1	2020	781,2	442,9
2008	623,9	494,2	2021	785,9	437,4

Source: Eurostat, GUS

Polish shipowners lack specialized vessels for container transport and ro-ro traffic, but the existing multi-use fleet can still be utilized for container transport. However, containers transportation is mostly limited by bridge clearances. On the Oder River, container transport in one layer is possible during high navigable water conditions, while two-layer transport is feasible at medium navigable water levels. Traditional motor barges can transport 12 to 16 TEU when stacked in two layers, while push fleets can accommodate more. For example, the BIZON III barge set can transport 24 to 30 TEU in one layer and 42 TEU in two layers.

Given the average gross weight of containers (12 tons), the cargo capacity of barges for one-layer transport is underutilized. With a draft of 1.6 meters, the OBP push barge's capacity is 475 tons, and the INBAT push barge's capacity is 587.5 tons. For one-layer transport, the OBP 500 utilizes 180 tons, and the INBAT utilizes 252 tons. For two-layer transport, the OBP 500 utilizes 360 tons, and the INBAT utilizes 504 tons.

Container transport on the lower Vistula (Gdansk-Tczew-Solec Kujawski) is also possible using the BIZON and INBAT sets. These push barges can transport two layers of containers regardless of their weight.

The operational fleet in Poland, while versatile, is significantly outdated. By the end of 2021, 90.1% of motor barges were built between 1949 and 1969, with no new motor barges constructed since 1980. Similarly, 97.7% of push barges were built before 1990, with only one push barge constructed after 2000. The continued operation of this aging fleet is reliant on constant repairs and modernization efforts.

Signs of fleet modernization in Poland are emerging, such as the launch of a new motor barge with hybrid propulsion (diesel + LNG) in 2022, with a tonnage of 400 tons and a draft of 60 cm. The future of Poland's inland waterway fleet is expected to be based on pushed sets, with modernization focusing on the construction of new push barges and low-emission pushers adapted for operation at a 60 cm draft.

2.3. Available infrastructure

The accessibility of inland water transport in Poland is shaped by the system of inland waterways and point infrastructure. This includes inland ports, which in Poland do not have the status of public ports, and are typically owned by private entities or riverside municipalities that lease them to interested parties. Additionally, loading berths owned by private entities are located on the waterways, and berths managed by the inland waterway (IWW) infrastructure authority are available for lease upon request.

An inventory of the components of inland waterways in Poland reveals that there are 134 facilities on the Odra Waterway and 54 on the Vistula Waterway. These facilities are classified as inland ports, harbors, marinas, trans-shipment berths, and factory trans-shipment facilities. Most of these infrastructures were constructed between 1970 and 1990, during the peak period of inland waterway transportation in Poland.

Historically, there are 18 reloading regions associated with the Odra Waterway, including Gliwice, Sławęcice, Łabędy, Kędzierzyn-Koźle, Opole, Wrocław, Malczyce, Głogów, Nowa Sól, Cigacice, Słubice, Kostrzyn nad Odrą, Osinów Dolny, Bielinek, Widuchowa, Gryfino, Szczecin, and Police. Additionally, transshipment operations were carried out in 11 other areas such as Chorula, Brzeg, Oława, Brzeg Dolny, Ścinawa, Chobienia, Bytom Odrzański, Krosno Odrzańskie, Urad, Chlevice, and Gozdowice.

Inland ports and transshipment facilities on the Odra River's main waterway are primarily located within the Gliwice Canal and the upper and middle sections of the Odra River. The lower section of the Odra River, however, lacks significant inland ports on the Polish side, with the major facility being the plant transshipment facility in Bielinek, operated by Szczecińskie Kopalnie Surowców Mineralnych S.A. In the Oder estuary area, there is no port exclusively linked to inland waterway transportation; river barge services are conducted at the wharves of the seaports of Szczecin, Świnoujście, Police, and Stepnica. The port in Świnoujście offers favorable conditions for barge service, having been designed with inland waterway fleets in mind. Conversely, the port of Szczecin faces several challenges, including a lack of designated wharves and facilities for inland waterway vessels, modern handling equipment, and appropriate berths for barges. Both ports require systemic solutions for the reception of ship waste from inland waterway transport units and the creation of a modern information platform for freight forwarders, ports, and IWW operators. The Port of Police, belonging to Grupa Azoty Zakłady Chemiczne "POLICE" S.A., and the port of Stepnica are well adapted for barge service.

The decline in the development of inland waterway transport in Poland, and the weakening condition of inland waterway shipowners, has resulted in the gradual municipalization or sale of river ports owned by shipping companies to private entities. This has led to a phenomenon described as "cargo drainage from IWW," where water-land transshipment is abandoned, and ports are repurposed for other economic functions such as storage, warehousing, production, and tourism. This trend has reduced the availability of inland water transport as a viable link in the supply chain. For example, the port of Cigacice lost its transshipment function, with operations ceasing in 2007 and the port being used primarily for coal storage before transitioning to a passenger port with facilities for small tourist vessels. Similar transformations

occurred at the ports in Nowa Sól, Bytom Odrzański, and Głogów, which have been converted into marinas and passenger harbors.

The lack of interest in developing inland waterway transport in Poland has even led to the liquidation of ports that were considered vital links in the early 21st century. In 2007, the port of Wrocław Popowice was decommissioned to make way for residential development. Additionally, the Wrocław City Port was sold to a private investor in 2020 and is being transformed into an office complex.

Attempts to improve accessibility to the Oder Waterway have faced obstacles. In the Kędzierzyn-Koźle area, two ports exist: the municipal port of Kędzierzyn-Koźle (Kędzierzyn-Koźle Terminals Company) and the plant port of Grupa Azoty. In 2017, the Kędzierzyn-Koźle Terminals Company sought to reactivate the port, planning to construct three wharves suitable for handling bulk products and containers, with an estimated handling capacity of 5 million tons per year. However, due to the lack of consent from PKP PLK SA for an access section to the port, investment work was suspended in 2019, and the dispute is being settled in court.

Currently, on the Oder River, transshipment functions related to cargo handling in the waterway-land are or can potentially be carried out in only about one-third of the existing point infrastructure facilities built for this purpose.

Table 5 Ports and reloading facilities on the Oder waterway

Lp.	Facility	Availability
1.	Gliwice Port	Not available
2.	Slawecice Wharf	No data
3.	Labedy Wharf	No data
4.	Azoty Plant Port Kędzierzyn-Koźle	Available
5.	Kędzierzyn-Koźle Municipal Port	Not available
6.	Gorazdze Cement Port Chorula	Not available
7.	FAMET Port Opole	Available
8.	Opole Municipal Port	Not available
9.	Brzeg Wharf	No data
10.	Wrocław Shipyard	Not available
11.	Malczyce Wharf	Available
12.	Malczyce Port	Available
13.	Ścinawa Port	Not available
14.	Głogów Port	Available
15.	Cigacice Port	Not available
16.	Urad Wharf	Not available
17.	Reloading Facility Rybocice	Not available
18.	Reloading Facility Kalerńsko	Not available
19.	Reloading Facility Bielinek	Not available
20.	Wharf Widuchowa	Not available
21.	Seaport Szczecin	Available

Source: Own Elaboration

The Vistula waterway is significantly less accessible due to the existing locations of river ports. Historically, there are 10 transshipment regions linked to the Lower Vistula waterway: Gdansk, Tczew, Korzeniewo,

Chelmno, Bydgoszcz, Solec Kujawski, Torun, Ciechocinek, Wloclawek, and Plock. On the middle and upper Vistula, the main transshipment points are located in Warsaw, Sandomierz, and Krakow.

The process of "turning away" from the reloading function of river ports is also evident along the Vistula waterway. For example, the port of Torun has been repurposed as a recreational and tourist basin, effectively excluding it from cargo shipping. The river port in Pulawy has been transformed into a yacht marina and cruise ship harbor. Similarly, the industrial areas of the Grudziądz port and its wharves have been adapted for tourist and recreational uses. The Warsaw Praga and Warsaw Żerań ports are not currently utilized for transshipment purposes. The Warsaw Praga river port ceased its transshipment operations in 1980, and there are now plans to develop a business and commercial complex in its place. Due to the long-term exclusion of the Żerań port from transport functions, city authorities are advocating for the adaptation of the port areas for residential, service, and leisure purposes.

The Płaszów port in Krakow has never functioned as a transshipment port. Its current capabilities are limited to shipyard activities, repair, and berthing. Similarly, the heavily silted port of Kujawy in Krakow has never performed reloading functions. The port of Sandomierz lost its significance as a transshipment point in 2019. Additionally, since 2021, the river port of Malbork (Nogat, adjacent to the Vistula River) has been closed due to a dispute over the repair of the railroad siding leading to the port.

Table 6 Ports and reloading facilities on the Vistula waterway

Lp.	Facility	Availability
1.	Reloading Facility Kraków	Not available
2.	Reloading Facility Kraków	Not available
3.	Kraków – Płaszów Port	Not available
4.	Kraków Nowa Huta Port	Not available
5.	Tursko Wharf	No data
6.	Lipnik Wharf	No data
7.	Otoka Grabińska Wharf	No data
8.	Sandomierz Port	Not available
9.	Zawichost Wharf	Not available
10.	Gołąb Reloading Facility	Not available
11.	Wilczkowice Górne Wharf	Not available
12.	Góra Kalwaria Port	No data
13.	Czerwieńsk Wharf	No data
14.	Wyszogród Wharf	No data
15.	Płock Port	Available
16.	Włocławek Port	No data
17.	Włocławek Anwil Wharf	Available
18.	Solbet Solec Kujawski Wharf	Available
19.	Bydgoszcz – Fordon Wharf	Available
20.	Bydgoszcz – Fordon Port	Available
21.	Chełmno Wharf	Available
22.	Korzeniewo Wharf	No data
23.	Tczew Wharf	Not available
24.	Kiezmark Wharf	Not available
25.	Malbork Wharf	Not available
26.	Port Malbork	Not available

Source: Own Elaboration

Currently, only a limited number of the existing transshipment points over waterways in Poland (ports and industrial transshipment wharves) are actively used for operations in conjunction with inland waterway transport. Table 6 illustrates this limited utilization. Inland ports recognized as international ports (E-ports) according to the AGN agreement—Kostrzyn nad Odrą, Wrocław, Kędzierzyn-Koźle, Gliwice, Bydgoszcz, and Warsaw—play a minor role in shaping the accessibility of inland waterway transport. Among these, the ports in the Kędzierzyn-Koźle and Bydgoszcz transshipment regions are more active in enhancing accessibility to inland waterway transport.

The current potential of inland waterway transport in Poland, given the existing locations of transshipment points (ports and factory transshipment berths), is not a limiting factor for inland waterway capacity. However, the anticipated significant increase in inland waterway transport in Poland, as projected in development programs, will depend on the designation of new transshipment points and the enhancement of the transshipment capacity of existing ports.

To achieve the projected cargo transportation volumes, approximately 20 new transshipment terminals need to be opened on the Odra Waterway in areas with high potential for generating cargo. These areas include Gliwice, Kędzierzyn-Koźle, Krapkowice, Chorula, Opole, Brzeg, Oława, Czernica, Wrocław, Malczyce, Lubiąż, Ścinawa, Głogów, Bytom Odrzański, Nowa Sól, Cigacice, Dobrzęcin, Krosno Odrzańskie, Urad, Słubice, and Kostrzyn nad Odrą. On the lower Vistula waterway, there is a need for approximately seven permanently operating transshipment regions: Płock, Włocławek, Toruń, Bydgoszcz, Chełmno, Korzeniowo, and Tczew.

3. IWW multi-use terminal concept

Desk research of the transshipment infrastructure available on the shipping routes indicates the need for its expansion and restoration to improve the accessibility of inland transportation and the possibility of its implementation as a link in multimodal transport chains. Therefore, one of the elements of support and recommendation to the authorities is the construction of a network of unionized transshipment wharves, the concept of which was prepared within the framework of the Cristal project.

General concept background

The development of efficient and sustainable inland waterway transshipment terminals is crucial for enhancing the logistics of goods transportation.(Sircar et al., 2016) This section explores the minimum infrastructure requirements and the operational layout for such terminals, drawing insights from existing literature and case studies.

In the context of water-water transshipment terminals, simulation-based quantitative analysis can provide valuable insights into the operational performance of different terminal layouts.(Zhu et al., 2019) Factors such as fluctuations in ship unloading efficiency and barge loading efficiency can significantly impact the overall productivity of the terminal.(Zhu et al., 2019)

Similarly, the emergence of new container terminal technologies and innovative operational models has been the focus of recent research in the maritime logistics domain.(Gharehgozli et al., 2014)These

advancements aim to improve container handling infrastructure and operational efficiency, which are directly applicable to inland waterway transshipment terminals.

The concept of a "Container Transferium" in the Port of Rotterdam provides a practical example of how an inland waterway transshipment terminal can enhance reliability and justify the costs of extra handling per container. (Froeling et al., 2008) By better planning of inland ships or "shuttles" and improving the handling of trucks, the Transferium can lead to increased reliability and efficiency in the hinterland transportation network.

In designing the minimum infrastructure requirements for an inland waterway transshipment terminal, key considerations should include the capacity and layout of berthing facilities, storage areas, cargo handling equipment, and intermodal connections. The operational layout should be optimized to minimize delays, maximize throughput, and ensure seamless integration with the broader transportation network.

By leveraging simulation-based analysis, innovative terminal technologies, and insights from practical case studies, this paper provides a framework for developing efficient and sustainable inland waterway transshipment terminals that can enhance the overall logistics and connectivity of the transportation system.

A typical structure of the inland waterway transshipment terminal should include:

- Berthing facilities: Sufficient quay length and depth to accommodate a range of inland vessels, including barges and smaller ships
- Storage and handling areas obligatory elements of a river port infrastructure
- Dedicated storage yards for temporary container and cargo storage, equipped with efficient cargo handling equipment such as gantry cranes, reach stackers, and forklifts.
- Multimodal connections: Seamless connections to road and rail networks to facilitate the intermodal transfer of goods
- Information and communication systems: Robust digital infrastructure to support real-time monitoring, planning, and coordination of terminal operations.
- Environmental and sustainability measures: Incorporation of green technologies and practices to reduce the terminal's environmental impact and ensure long-term sustainability.
- Flexible and scalable design: The terminal's layout and infrastructure should be designed to accommodate future growth and changes in cargo volumes and transportation patterns.
- Efficient cargo handling processes: Optimization of cargo handling workflows, including loading, unloading, and transshipment operations, to minimize delays and optimize throughput.
- Adequate space for support facilities: Offices, maintenance workshops, and other ancillary structures to support terminal operations.
- Redundancy and resilience: Incorporation of backup systems and contingency plans to ensure the terminal's operational continuity in the face of disruptions or emergencies.

- Integrated with the broader logistics network: The terminal should be designed to seamlessly integrate with the wider transportation and logistics ecosystem, enabling efficient movement of goods and enhancing the overall supply chain performance.
- Automation and digitalization: Leveraging technology-driven solutions, such as automated cargo handling equipment and digital information systems, to boost productivity, safety, and efficiency.
- Operational flexibility: The terminal should be designed to accommodate a diverse range of cargo types and transportation modes, ensuring its ability to adapt to changing market demands and evolving logistics requirements.
- Workforce development: Investing in the training and upskilling of terminal personnel to maintain high levels of operational expertise and safety
- Risk management: Proactive assessment and mitigation of potential risks, including operational, safety, and environmental risks, to ensure the terminal's long-term viability and sustainability.
- Regulatory compliance: Adherence to relevant national and international regulations governing inland waterway transportation, environmental protection, and port operations.

By considering these minimum infrastructure requirements and incorporating best practices in the operational layout, inland waterway transshipment terminals can be designed to enhance the efficiency, reliability, and sustainability of the overall transportation network.(Budyanto & Fernanda, 2020)(Grass & Lepekhina, 2023)(Gharehgozli et al., 2014)

Complementary to the above mentioned elements, the terminal layout should also consider the unique characteristics of the local and regional transportation networks, as well as the specific cargo handling requirements of the terminal's target market.(Humphreys et al., 2019)(Dinu et al., 2017). And from the other hand, also the operability of a terminal should be focused on the following goals:

- Optimization of operational layout of inland ship/barge schedules and truck arrivals Coordination with hinterland logistics chain to ensure reliable and timely cargo delivery
- Utilization of advanced information systems and real-time dataUtilization of advanced container handling technologies, e.g. automated stacking cranes
- Minimize travel distances and turnaround times for ships/barges
- Ensure smooth coordination between different modes of transportation
- Implement advanced information systems for real-time visibility and planning
- Automation and digitalization to enhance productivity and reliability
- Leverage simulation modeling to test and refine the terminal layout

In conclusion, the development of efficient and sustainable inland waterway transshipment terminals is crucial for enhancing the overall logistics and connectivity of the transportation system. By considering the minimum infrastructure requirements and optimizing the operational layout, terminal operators can improve reliability, justify the costs of extra handling, and contribute to the overall efficiency of the supply chain.(Froeling et al., 2008)(Gharehgozli et al., 2014).

Inland terminal parametrization

An inland waterway terminal can be described by the following measures related to the infrastructure: (Zhu et al., 2019)(Hervás-Peralta et al., 2020)(Gharehgozli et al., 2014)(Humphreys et al., 2019)

- quay length [m]
- water depth [cm]
- number of barges slots/positions
- storage capacity [m², TEU]
- refrigerated container slots [TEU]
- number of handling equipment like gantry cranes, reach stackers, forklifts
- max. weight for above equipment
- number of truck slots
- number of rail sidings

Above measures provide a clear picture of the terminal's capacity and capabilities for handling different cargo types and volumes efficiently. However, inland waterway terminal operations are also influenced by external factors such as weather, water levels, and interactions with the hinterland logistics network.(Rusinov et al., 2018)(Dinu et al., 2017). There are also another factor affecting the layout and operability of a terminal like the ownership and management structure, customs/regulatory requirements, labor practices etc.

It is often to be observed a dedicated terminal, or wharf dedicated to only one stakeholder/owner, would have a different operational layout compared to a common-user terminal managed by public port authority.(Rusinov et al., 2018) This means not only public inaccessibility of the terminal, but also cargo-specific layout and transshipment equipment.

Additionally, the terminal design should take into account the forecasted cargo demand, transportation mode shifts, and regulations regarding environmental performance to ensure long-term viability.(Li et al., 2021)

Country-specified River terminal concept

Taking into consideration specificity of the Polish pilot environment and market size, majority of the existing inland waterways ports are out of operation and only few of them are in operation in a limited scale. This leads to the conclusion, that in case of any new transport activity on the Polish navigable rivers should appear, the sufficient infrastructure should be deployed, at least on a small scale.

A small size intermodal terminal is meant as a transshipment node with the surface below 40,000 m², basically equipped with one mobile crane or forklift or reachstacker, with a yearly turnover below 50,000 TEU (ed. Czermanski, 2021), which equals to ca. 500,000 tons of cargo.

In this regard, following minimum parameters should be ensured for a basic transshipment node (inland port/wharf):

- total terminal area by 5,000 m²,
- quay length 100.0 m,

- number of barges slot/position: 1,
- water depth at quay 2.7 m,
- storage area by 600 m²,
- heavy lift operation area 1,600 m²,
- working area 2,000 m²,
- administration building 500 m²,
- storage tent 800 m²,
- other area 700 m²,

Besides, the whole area should be sufficiently constructed to enable rolling of any type of equipment and vehicles with appropriate load capacity.

Terminal pavements are among the most heavily loaded and carry loads at a level 10 times higher than roads. The dynamic load from container mobile cranes (Reach Stackers), transmitted to the front axle during the lifting and moving the container, range from 1,000 kN to 1,200 kN. Loads static loads from stacked containers exert very high contact pressures via the corner feet. With four 30 tonne containers, it reaches a value of 10.4 MPa. By comparison, on EU roads the maximum axle load is 115 kN, while the contact pressure under the wheels of heavy vehicles does not exceeds 1.0 MPa. In addition, terminal pavements, like road surfaces are exposed to thermal stress and environmental aggression caused by cyclic freezing and thawing (exposure class XF4). (Falkowski, 2104)

The quays should have the same, increased resilience against cargo load during transshipment. Therefore Larssens's walls have been selected as a conceptual design of the terminal alongside the river. The pavement of the terminal should be constructed of a low alkali, sulphate-resistant Portland cement CEM I 42.5 N-NA/HSR at 360kg/m³ the concrete mix. The aggregate fine should be washed sand, sand point 35%. The foreseen coarse aggregate of granite and basalt grits was assumed. The content of grains smaller than 0.25 mm (cement and sand) in 1 m³ mixture should not exceed 420 kg/m³. The concrete was modified with a bitumen emulsion admixture to reduce water absorption and improve tightness and resistance to environmental aggression.

Despite of the above crucial construction elements, there are planned another complementary infrastructure elements:

- open yards: used for the storage of bulky goods, bulk materials and other loads that do not require cover,
- covered warehouses: used for the storage of goods requiring protection from the weather,
- access roads and manoeuvring yards: allow truck access to the terminal and transshipment operations,
- rail tracks: allow cargo to be transported directly to and from the terminal,
- information systems (TOS): managing traffic and transshipment operations,
- security and monitoring systems: ensuring the protection of the site and goods,
- office buildings: intended for the administration and management of terminal operations,
- workshops: areas for servicing and repairing transshipment equipment,
- social facilities: providing comfort for employees (canteens, changing rooms, etc.),
- transformer stations: providing electricity to terminal equipment,
- tanks and fuel stations: to supply fuel to vessels and transshipment equipment.

A graphical layout of such conceptual terminal can be seen on the Figure 1

Figure 1 IWW terminal concept - sketch layout

Source: Own elaboration.

Preparation and construction costs

The cost estimate for the construction of a river terminal includes a number of elements that make up the total cost of implementing this type of investment. Key elements of the cost estimate include:

- ✓ Land and site preparation costs:
 - Purchase or lease of land. In the concept this cost has been skipped due to the assumption of the owners investment into the terminal/wharf.
 - Preparatory works such as site levelling, vegetation removal, earthworks and ground reinforcement.
- ✓ Design and engineering costs:
 - Cost of developing architectural, structural, technical and environmental designs.
 - Cost of engineering supervision and project management.
- ✓ Construction of quay and harbour infrastructure:

- Cost of constructing berths and jetties.
- Installation of shoreline reinforcement and mooring systems.
- ✓ Purchase and installation of handling equipment:
 - Cost of purchasing cranes, cranes, conveyor belts and container lifts. In the concept have been assumed second hand used vehicles in order to minimize the purchase cost.
 - Cost of installing and commissioning this equipment.
- ✓ Construction of storage yards and warehouses:
 - Cost of constructing storage yards (open and enclosed).
 - Cost of construction of covered warehouses and loading halls. In the concept was assumed artificial tent which can play the role of a standard warehouse, to minimize the purchase cost.
- ✓ Construction of road and rail infrastructure:
 - Cost of constructing access roads and car parks. No marshalling yards nor sidings were assumed.
- ✓ Installation of management and control systems:
 - Cost of purchasing and installing IT systems to manage terminal operations.
 - Cost of security and monitoring systems.
- ✓ Cost of technical and welfare facilities:
 - Construction of office buildings, workshops and welfare facilities.
 - Equipping these facilities with the necessary equipment and furniture.
- ✓ Energy and fuel costs:
 - Construction of transformer stations and electrical installations.
 - Installation of fuel tanks and stations for vessels and handling equipment.
- ✓ Administrative and legal costs:
 - Fees for permits and licences.
 - Costs related to legal formalities, public consultations and environmental studies.

The cost estimate for the construction of the river terminal must be carefully prepared, taking into account all of the above elements, in order to ensure a realistic assessment of costs and to enable effective management of the project budget.

For the proposed terminal concept the estimated cost reached amount of 5,000,000 EUR with above listed technical parameters. The basic values of the individual cost items are indicated in the below table.

Table 7 *Estimated investment costs*

Infrastructure		
Dredging works	650 000,00	EUR
Quay construction	1 000 000,00	EUR
Storage area	450 000,00	EUR
Buildings	300 000,00	EUR
Supply installations	100 000,00	EUR
Working area	500 000,00	EUR

Tent	200 000,00	EUR
Other area	250 000,00	EUR
Other works	250 000,00	EUR
TOTAL	3 700 000,00	EUR
Documentation		
Design	150 000,00	EUR
Approvals	100 000,00	EUR
Inspections	50 000,00	EUR
TOTAL	300 000,00	EUR
Equipment		
Liebherr TM1090	600 000,00	EUR
RS	300 000,00	EUR
Car	30 000,00	EUR
Forklift	70 000,00	EUR
TOTAL	1 000 000,00	EUR
GRAND TOTAL	5 000 000,00	EUR

Source: own calculations.

It should be emphasised that the above valuation is only an estimate of the cost of building the river terminal without the cost of purchasing the property, but including all the necessary elements of construction and the documentation and technical acceptance phase to allow the terminal to be operated.

The unit values used to determine the value of these cost items are in line with the values of similar construction works for Polish conditions according to market conditions in spring 2024 in the Pomeranian Voivodeship.

However, it is possible to obtain different values for these works each time, depending on the country, region, current market situation and many other external factors in the hydraulic engineering sector.

4. Building supply chains in limited infrastructure conditions - temporary reloading facility

Desk research conducted in the previous chapter revealed numerous potential reloading locations along the Oder and Vistula rivers. However, most of these locations lack reloading equipment. Further development of IWT-based supply chains requires significant investments or a state strategic plan to develop a network of reliable reloading facilities. A natural consequence of such a strategy is the

development of sustainable and coherent hinterland infrastructure, such as roads and railway networks connected to inland waterway wharfs and terminals which example has been presented in previous chapter.

Until such investments are made, supply chain operators, including freight forwarders, 3PL operators, and skippers, are compelled to arrange temporary reloading facilities. Although these solutions adhere to European standards, setting up temporary facilities incurs additional time and costs. This, in turn, impacts stakeholders' willingness to integrate IWT into their supply chains.

Geographical location

An IWW temporary reloading facility must be tailored to the scheduled cargo quantity and the barge deployed for IWW operations, ensuring last-mile access and smooth operations. Furthermore, according to the combined transport definition, the terminal should not be more than 150 km from the final delivery location. Desk research conducted within the framework of WP9 showed that, for economic reasons and to minimize total supply chain costs, this distance should not exceed 50 km.

Wharf parameters

Minimum required wharf parameters are determined by main factors:

- Deployed barge length
- Maximum quay load
- Maximum storage area

The length of the quay required for reloading is one of the key aspects in selecting a location for a temporary reloading point. For the safety of mooring the vessel and the smooth execution of logistics operations, it is necessary to choose a quay that is longer than the total length of the vessel. In extreme cases, reloading can be accomplished by moving the vessel along the quay during reloading operations to achieve the reach of the reloading equipment. However, this approach increases reloading costs and extends the handling time of the vessel. Considering the average length of a barge with a pusher is approximately 70 meters, quays with a minimum length of 100 meters are optimal.

In addition to the length of the quay itself, securing the quay in terms of permissible working load is equally important. Most quays allow for the unrestricted reloading of heavy pieces. However, the load capacity of the quay becomes particularly crucial during the storage of cargo, especially stacked loaded containers. The permissible load parameter of the quay, should be included in lease agreement between the voyage operator and the landowner or administrator.

In the vast majority of logistics models, reloading at inland waterway quays occurs through intermediate stages. This means that cargo from the barge's deck is not transferred directly to another mode of transport but is temporarily stored in a storage yard until delivery to the final recipient is scheduled. The size and equipment of the storage yard primarily depend on the type and quantity of cargo being handled. In practice, it is often assumed that the storage yard should have a capacity equivalent to three times the largest unit calling at the reloading quay. However, this assumption mainly applies to regular shipping

operations. For one-time reloading operations at a temporary quay, the capacity of the planned unit to be reloaded will suffice.

Another critical issue, particularly when storing goods at the quay for an extended period, is ensuring the security of the cargo and restricting access to the reloading and storage area to unauthorized persons. A good practice is to hire companies specializing in property protection, which will secure the cargo and limit the movement of unauthorized persons within the reloading and storage area, thereby enhancing the safety of the operations.

An additional consideration is verifying access to the selected quay in terms of road infrastructure before commencing reloading operations. It is the duty of the voyage operator to check the access roads for any spatial or infrastructural restrictions, such as traffic bans imposed by the road manager.

Of course, organizing a temporary reloading site involves not only infrastructure but also the appropriate reloading equipment. This equipment must be tailored to the type and weight of the cargo to be reloaded and stored at the quay. In most cases, mobile cranes with suitable attachments, such as clamps, traverses, or grabs for bulk cargo, are successfully used. The size and required lifting capacity of the equipment depend on the weight of the cargo being lifted and the distance and height to which it will be raised. The following table shows example values for a crane with a maximum lifting capacity of 160 tons.

Table 8 Mobile crane lifting range

	13 m	17,5 m	22 m	26,5 m	31 m	35,5 m	40 m	44,6 m	49,1 m	53,6 m	58,1 m	62 m	m
160	115												3
115	107	96											3,5
104	99	96	94	78									4
95	91	89	85	76	63								4,5
89	85	84	80	74	62	50							5
79	74	74	72	69	60	49	38						6
65	64	65	64	63	58	47,5	36	28,4					7
56	56	56	56	56	55	46	34,5	27,3					8
48	48	49	49,5	49	48,5	44	32,5	26,1	21,5				9
42,5	42,5	43	43,5	43	42,5	42,5	30,5	24,9	20,8	17			10
40	40	40,5	41	40,5	40	40,5	29,8	24,2	20,4	16,8	14		10,5
		38,5	38,5	38	39	38,5	28,9	23,6	19,9	16,5	13,9		11
		34,5	34,5	34	35	34,5	27,2	22,4	19,1	16	13,6	11,5	12
		28,1	28,2	29	28,7	28,1	24,4	20,1	17,5	15	12,8	11	14
		26	25,8	26,5	26,2	25,6	23,1	19,2	16,7	14,4	12,5	10,7	15
			24,3	24,3	23,9	23,3	21,8	18,3	15,9	13,9	12,1	10,4	16
			20,7	20,7	20,3	19,7	19,1	16,6	14,6	12,8	11,3	9,8	18
			18,5	18,5	18,1	17,5	17,3	15,4	13,6	12,1	10,7	9,4	19,5
				17,8	17,4	16,8	16,7	15,1	13,3	11,8	10,6	9,2	20
				15,5	15,1	14,6	15,1	13,8	12,2	10,9	9,9	8,7	22
				13,7	13,2	13,5	13,2	12,3	11,3	10,1	9,2	8,2	24
					11,7	12,2	11,6	11,1	10,3	9,4	8,6	7,7	26
					10,9	10,8	10,3	9,9	9,3	8,7	8	7,2	28
						9,7	9,1	9,4	8,6	8	7,5	6,7	30
						8,7	8,2	8,4	7,8	7,3	6,9	6,3	32
							7,8	7,5	7,2	6,7	6,5	5,8	34
							7,3	6,7	6,7	6,3	6,1	5,4	36
								6	6	5,8	5,4	5,1	38
								5,5	5,4	5,3	4,9	4,8	40
								5,4	5	4,9	4,5	4,5	42
									4,6	4,4	4,1	4,1	44
									4,3	4,1	3,7	3,7	46
										3,7	3,4	3,4	48
										3,4	3	3	50
											2,6	2,6	52
											2,3	2,3	54
												2	56
												1,7	58

Source: <http://dzwigi.org>

As an example, the following facility has been arranged for reloading 40-foot High Cube (40'HC) containers from a barge to the quay and subsequently onto trucks. A set comprising a pusher and a 370 GT barge, with a total length of approximately 70 meters, is berthed at a 60-meter quay. Containers weighing 26 tons each are reloaded into a storage area using a 150-ton crane. The berth has been divided into three distinct areas:

- Reloading Area:
 - Dedicated space for crane operations.
 - Equipped with a 150-ton crane capable of handling the weight and size of the containers.
 - Ensures safe and efficient transfer of containers from the barge to the quay.
 - Storage Area:
- Designed area for temporary storage of containers.
 - Located adjacent to the reloading area for smooth transfer of containers.
 - Capacity aligned with operational requirements to accommodate the incoming cargo.
- Trucks Loading Area:
 - Designated space for loading containers onto trucks.
 - Provides easy access to the state road for onward transportation.
 - Ensures seamless integration with the broader logistics network.

This setup ensures efficient reloading operations while maintaining the safety and integrity of the cargo. The visible division of the berth into these functional areas facilitates smooth operations and optimizes the use of space and equipment. Below picture clearly shows the indicated areas. From the left – truck access, front – reloading area, back – container storage area.

Figure 2 Temporary reloading facility with indicated operation areas

Source: Own archive

Demand market analysis

The traditional application area of inland waterway transport is primarily associated with handling the demand for transporting unprocessed, low-value goods that are not sensitive to transit time. The demand for inland waterway transport depends on this sector's ability to integrate into the system of transporting higher-value, processed goods. Relying solely on traditional transport (raw materials and other low-value goods) would significantly limit the scope of this sector's activities. Analyzing trends in the structure of sold production reveals an increase in the processing sector's production and a decline in the mining and extraction sectors.

In Poland, from 2005 to 2021, the value of sold production in the processing industry increased 2.4 times, while in mining and extraction it decreased by 11.5%. Consequently, the share of the processing industry's sold production in total industrial production sales at the national level rose from 83.1% to 85.3%, while in mining and extraction it fell from 5.1% to 3.3% (GUS, 2022)². Therefore, it is expected that inland waterway

² Rocznik Statystyczny Przemysłu, GUS, Warszawa 2022, <https://stat.gov.pl/obszary-tematyczne/roczniki-statystyczne/roczniki-statystyczne/rocznik-statystyczny-przemyslu-2022,5,16.html> (dostęp: 28.12.2023).

transport in Poland will gradually integrate into the intermodal transport system, thereby taking over part of the container transport currently handled by road transport.

In 2022, road transport within intermodal transport in Poland moved over 25 million tons of containerized cargo. The majority of these transports were to/from intermodal terminals located in Poland, constituting 98.6% of total intermodal transports by road in 2022. Most cargo was transported to/from the following voivodeships: Łódź (26.2%), Pomerania (15.4%), Silesia (12.3%), Lower Silesia (11.2%), and Lesser Poland (10.4%)(GUS, 2023) This distribution indicates that regions directly linked to the inland waterway network are also among the leaders in generating demand for container transport.

Considering that the National Inland Waterway Development Program (KPŻ 2030) anticipates the stabilization of navigation conditions on the Oder and lower Vistula rivers post-2030, it is expected—following the paradigm of intermodal shifts—that some container transport will move to inland waterways, especially in the Pomeranian, Kuyavian-Pomeranian, Silesian, and Lower Silesian voivodeships. To estimate the potential portion of road container transport that could be shifted to inland waterways in these voivodeships, we referred to European experiences and calculated the average takeover index (d) for EU countries using the following formula:

$$d = \frac{C_{IWW}}{C_R},$$

where:

C_{IWW} – IWW containerised cargo volume,

C_R – road containerised cargo volume.

Initially, these indices were calculated for individual countries with notable inland waterway container transport. To avoid random fluctuations, the values were averaged for 2020-2022. The analysis revealed a wide variation in indices, ranging from 0.03% in Austria to 48.3% in the Netherlands and even 93.3% in Belgium. To avoid artificially inflating the EU-wide index, outliers were excluded. The averaged index (d) for the study period was 4.6%.

According to KPŻ 2030, inland waterway freight transport in Poland could increase to 6.8 million tons annually by 2030. The share of container transport is estimated at 6.97%, which translates to approximately 475.0 thousand tons. Achieving this volume would imply a takeover index (d) of 4.0 in Poland, closely matching EU conditions. However, given Poland's lack of experience with inland waterway container transport, such a shift level is unrealistic. A more plausible assumption is a takeover index of 2.5% by 2030.

The estimated demand for inland waterway container transport in a given region

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} C_{IWW} + C_R = C_{R+IWW} \\ \frac{C_{IWW}}{C_R} = d \end{array} \right\}$$

Where

$$C_R = \frac{C_{IWW}}{d}$$

$$C_{IWW} + \frac{C_{IWW}}{d} = C_{R+IWW}$$

$$dC_{IWW} + C_{IWW} = dC_{R+IWW}$$

$$C_{IWW}(d + 1) = dC_{R+IWW}$$

$$C_{IWW} = \frac{dC_{R+IWW}}{d + 1}$$

The shift of containerized cargo volumes from road to inland waterway transport will likely be facilitated by updating current high navigable water (WWŻ) indicators. Indicators established in the 1940s in Poland no longer reflect current conditions and may exceed warning and alarm levels. Consequently, bridge clearances are underestimated, limiting container navigation. KPŻ 2030 aims to update WWŻ indicators for the Vistula and Oder rivers and reclassify them. The reclassification will occur in two stages in 2024 and 2030 after updating the WWŻ indicator by 2028.

This measure is expected to remove some constraints caused by insufficient bridge heights without requiring reconstruction, thus enabling more effective container traffic shifts from road to inland waterway transport. Investment and organizational measures outlined in KPŻ 2030 will stabilize water levels and restore conditions for reliable inland waterway transport services. These positive developments will likely increase demand for waterway transport. Businesses increasingly consider sustainable logistics in their development strategies, so as reliable inland waterway services are restored in Poland, there will be growing interest in utilizing inland navigation as a logistics link.

Demand on Oder waterway

A significantly higher priority in the KPŻ2030 was given to the need to restore stable conditions for inland navigation on the Odra waterway. The program includes the modernization of regulatory structures (on the free-flowing Odra) and the completion of investments at existing waterway locks (modernization of locks and weirs) on the canalized Odra. Unlike the plans for the lower Vistula, these investments have the status of priority works. It is expected that as a result of implementing KPŻ2030, the technical parameters specified in the classification of inland waterways will be restored, achieving Good Navigational Conditions, enabling regular, uninterrupted, and safe freight navigation over the longest stretches of rivers.

As previously demonstrated, the economic potential, especially in such voivodeships as Silesian, Opole, Lower Silesian, and West Pomeranian, significantly influences the demand for cargo transport via the Odra waterway. Also, from the analysis of the distribution of potential shippers in the Odra waterway region it is evident that there is a large supply of bulk dry goods:

- the area of Silesia, Opole, Lower Silesia, and Szczecin (mainly the seaport in Szczecin) – for bulk dry goods;

- the region of the so-called Wrocław Functional Area and the Szczecin and Police area (seaports) – for liquid bulk goods;
- the area of the Silesian and Lower Silesian voivodeships, especially the Wrocław Functional Area – for container and potentially containerized general cargo.

Assuming that the need to strengthen the position of inland water transport in the transport system will not lose its importance and the plans for the development of inland navigation specified in KPŻ2030 will be consistently implemented, it can be expected that freight transport on the Odra will reach 6 million tons annually after 2030. These transports will primarily be carried out:

- between the seaports of Szczecin and Świnoujście – the Federal Republic of Germany, and
- on the upper Odra section, especially serving urban agglomerations and industrial areas near Wrocław, Opole, and Gliwice

The main cargo group will be bulk dry goods. Assuming, according to the assumptions of KPŻ2030, that the share of this cargo group in total transport in Poland will be approximately 65%, it can be predicted that the transport of this cargo group on the Odra after 2030 will amount to 3.9 million tons. The share of liquid bulk goods in the total volume of transport is estimated at 4.1%. Therefore, it is anticipated that such transports on the Odra after 2030 will amount to 246 thousand tons (mainly in the Szczecin region and Lower Silesian voivodeship).

Figure 3 Estimated distribution of cargo transport on the Odra waterway by loading and unloading regions after 2030 (million tons)

*Transport volumes do not sum due to transport relations between loading and unloading locations located in different voivodeship

Source: Own elaboration based on: Resolution No. 180/2023 of the Council of Ministers of October 3, 2023, establishing a development program under the name "National Navigational Program until 2030" (annex to the resolution).

The stabilization of navigation conditions on the Odra will facilitate the inclusion of inland water transport in handling container transports and other general cargo. According to the previously adopted takeover rated of 2.5%, it can be predicted that container transports on the Odra after 2030 could reach approximately 135 thousand tons (Table below). The volume of other general cargo transports is estimated at 1.7 million tons. Transporting oversized loads will remain an important sphere of application for inland water transport. It is expected that after 2030, transports of this cargo group (with main loading locations in the Opole and Wrocław regions) will amount to approximately 3.4 thousand tons annually.

Table 9 *Estimated distribution of demand for container transport on the Odra waterway after 2030 assuming a takeover rate $d = 2.5\%$ (ton figure)*

Region	C_{R+IWW} (th. ton)	dC_{R+IWW}	Rise rate ($d + 1$)	C_{IWW} (th. ton)	C_R (th. ton)
Silesian	2774,5	69,4	1,025	67,7	2706,8
Lower Silesian	2572,1	64,3	1,025	62,7	2509,3
West Pomeranian	186,4	4,7	1,025	4,5	181,9
Total				134,9	5398,0

Source: Own elaboration

More advanced investment work on the Odra waterway is planned in the multi-year program "Development of the Central Odra". The program envisages the continuation of cascade development on the Odra from 2024 to 2030. To stabilize the water level below the Malczyce water gate built in 2018, the program includes the construction of additional water locks at Lubiąż and Ścinawa. It is estimated that implementing the goals of this program would increase transport volumes on the Odra after 2030 to 7.5 million tons annually. This program currently does not have a binding character due to the project status of the resolution.

Considering the experiences associated with the construction of the Malczyce water gate, the prospect of building the Lubiąż and Ścinawa water locks by 2030 may seem overly optimistic. This may be indicated by experiences related to the prolonged construction of the Malczyce water gate, which has been under construction since 1997 and has not yet been fully completed. In June 2018, only a sluice gate was put into use (therefore, the level allows for the sluicing of floating objects), but the completion deadline for this project as a whole (including backwater construction) is scheduled for 2026. International experiences also indicate the time-consuming nature of such investments, for example, related to the construction of additional lock chambers on the Weser, Moselle, and Neckar waterways to increase their throughput. The construction of an additional lock chamber in Zeltingen on the Moselle alone lasted 7 years (2003-2010, excluding administrative work). A similar duration was required for the construction of another lock in Minden on the middle section of the Weser (2010-2017).

Nevertheless, the implementation of the multi-year program "Development of the Central Odra" would contribute to extending the canalized section of the Odra to Ścinawa and, consequently, stabilize navigation conditions on this waterway. Unlike free-flowing river sections, canalized waterways are less susceptible to water level changes. Therefore, implementing the program may improve the attractiveness of cargo transport via this waterway and, consequently, contribute to increased demand for transport.

Demand on Vistula waterway

The greatest potential for the development of inland navigation on the Vistula River exists on its lower section. The increase in transport function for this section is anticipated in KPŻ 2030. It is expected that by 2030, cargo transport on the lower Vistula could increase to approximately 0.8 million tons annually.

Transport on the lower Vistula will be primarily concentrated in the regions of Pomeranian and Kuyavian-Pomeranian voivodeships (as shown in the figure below). The significance of the lower Vistula section is mainly due to the dynamic development of the seaport in Gdańsk and the substantial potential of the logistic hub, which is projected to include the Bydgoszcz-Solec Kujawski multimodal platform and the Bydgoszcz Emilianowo intermodal terminal. This hub is strategically located to handle cargo between the seaports in Gdańsk and Gdynia and major urban areas in the country, such as Łódź, Warsaw, and Poznań, utilizing all modes of transport.

Figure 4 Estimated distribution of cargo transport on the lower Vistula waterway by loading and unloading regions after 2030 (million tons).

**The cargo volumes do not sum up due to transport relations between loading and unloading points located in different voivodeships*

Source: Own elaboration based on: Resolution No. 180/2023 of the Council of Ministers of October 3, 2023, establishing the development program titled "National Shipping Program until 2030" (annex to the resolution).

The main cargo group will consist of dry bulk goods – mainly aggregates. It can be assumed that the share of this cargo group in total transport on this waterway will be around 56%. Therefore, it is anticipated that the transport of this cargo group on the lower Vistula will reach about 450,000 tons by 2030. The share of liquid bulk goods is estimated at around 4%, which means that the transport of this cargo group could reach about 32,000 tons annually by 2030.

It is expected that the stabilization of navigational conditions will integrate this section of the waterway into the supply chains of general cargo. Estimates suggest that the transport of general cargo, not subject to containerization, will be about 155,000 tons annually by 2030. A new area for inland waterway transport will be container transport. According to the previously assumed capture rate of 2.5%, container transport

on this section could reach 157.2 thousand tons (Table 9). Due to the role of the seaport in Gdańsk, this transport will be concentrated in the Pomeranian Voivodeship as the loading and unloading region (134.5 thousand tons). In the Kuyavian-Pomeranian Voivodeship, as the loading and unloading region, container transport is estimated at 22.7 thousand tons. Therefore, container transport would constitute 19.6% of the projected total transport on this section of the Vistula. The significance of the lower Vistula waterway in the transport of oversized cargo will be maintained. The demand for the transport of this cargo group after 2030 is estimated at about 5 thousand tons annually.

Table 10 *Estimated distribution of demand for container transport on the lower Vistula waterway in 2030 with an assumed capture rate of 2.5%*

Region	C_{R+IWW} (th. ton)	dC_{R+IWW}	$d + 1$	C_{IWW} (th. ton)	C_R (th. ton)
Pomeranian	5514,8	137,9	1,025	134,5	5380,3
Kuyavian-Pomeranian	930,3	23,3	1,025	22,7	907,6
Total				157,2	6287,9

Source: Own elaboration

It can be expected that the transport function of the lower Vistula waterway will increase as a result of the investment assumptions outlined in the long-term program "Comprehensive Development of the Lower Vistula." The program includes the construction of the Siarzewo water stage below the existing Włocławek stage by 2032. It is anticipated that the implementation of the program, in the part relating to inland navigation, will significantly improve the capacity of the Vistula on the Gdańsk-Włocławek section, thereby strengthening the integration of the seaport in Gdańsk with its hinterland. It is projected that the commissioning of the Siarzewo water stage and the reconstruction of the regulatory structures will allow the transfer of approximately 280,000 tons of cargo annually from road transport to the lower Vistula waterway. Therefore, it is expected that after 2032, transport on this section of the Vistula will be around 1.1 million tons. However, this level would still be significantly lower than the transport volumes achieved in the 1980s. It is estimated that during this period, the former Bydgoszcz Shipping Company transported about 2 million tons of cargo annually on this section.

To gain better understanding on potential demand for IWW transport and obtain other point of view on IWT a research during direct telephone interviews among 70 enterprises in the TSL (Transport, Forwarding, Logistics) industry was conducted.. This survey is part of a larger project examining the possibilities for the development and integration of various forms of transport within national and international logistics. The data collected so far provide preliminary results that outline the current situation and perception of inland waterway transport while simultaneously analyzing companies' readiness for its adoption. The estimated transport potential in the Vistula and Oder river basins is defined by respondents at approximately 5%, reflecting a significant need for further research and development actions in this field especially in IWT awareness and knowledge on IWT implementation into supply chains.

Dominant Activity Area in Cargo Transporting

Respondents clearly identify their leading activity area in inland transport, with the majority pointing to the Oder Region (46.67%) and the Vistula Region (40%).

Annual Cargo Mass in Domestic Import

A decisive majority of companies (93.33%) handle cargo in domestic import with a mass of up to 10,000 tons annually, indicating a relatively small participation in mass cargo transportation.

Key Seaports for Transport Companies

Świnoujście (46.67%) is recognized as a key seaport in the operations of transport companies, with Gdynia (40%) and Gdańsk (33.33%) following, emphasizing their importance in maritime logistics.

Use of Own Transport Means

Companies are divided on the issue of having their own means of transport, with a slight majority of those that do use their own fleet (53.33%), mainly trucks.

Readiness to implement Inland Waterway Transport (IWT)

The survey results indicate a very low readiness among firms to adapt inland waterway transport (IWT) into their current operations. As many as 93.33% of respondents rated their readiness at the lowest level of the scale (1 out of 5), suggesting significant barriers to implementing this form of transport. This may be due to a lack of infrastructure, insufficient industry knowledge, or the perception of IWT as an unprofitable investment. This situation underscores the need for market education and investments in infrastructure supporting inland waterway transport.

Perception of Inland Waterway Transport in Poland

Inland waterway transport in Poland is currently perceived by surveyed companies primarily as technically challenging and requiring specialized knowledge (80% of responses), as well as a form of transport without future prospects (60% of responses). This perspective of the respondents may reflect the current technological and administrative challenges that deter companies from investing in this type of transport and a lack of belief in its developmental prospects. To change this negative image, promotional activities are necessary, along with demonstrating the successes and benefits of inland waterway transport in other regions.

Factors Motivating the Inclusion of Inland Waterway Transport

The main factor that would convince companies to include inland waterway transport in their offer is the lower cost of such services compared to currently preferred methods (93.33% of responses). This indicates that price competitiveness is a key decision-making element for transport companies. Respondents also pay attention to the need to improve navigational conditions on rivers (33.33% of responses), highlighting that infrastructure and operational conditions play an essential role in the potential choice of IWT as a complementary solution in supply chains.

Carbon Footprint Analysis in Transport Project

The companies in the survey unanimously (100%) indicate that they do not analyze the carbon footprint when preparing transport projects, which may suggest a lack of awareness or tools for such analysis.

Cargo Flow

The utilization level of reloading potential in inland waterway ports can be exemplified by the volume of reloading activities. In Poland, decades of neglect in the development of inland waterways have led to a systematic decline in cargo transportation volumes, subsequently diminishing the utilization of point infrastructure reloading facilities such as ports and industrial reloading wharves. This declining trend has resulted in the closure of some ports and a gradual reduction in handling facilities at existing ports, thereby reducing port handling capacity.

Table 11 Cargo turnover in Polish IWW ports [tonnes]

Year	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Bielinek	297 328	329 269	424 117	277 863	249 926	380 687	263 380	182 482
Bydgoszcz	917 510	779 624	823 685	140 122	1 344	296	205	84
Cigacice	:	46	350	120	:	:	:	:
Gliwice	28 970	316 020	182 648	214 278	50 920	28 060	16 920	3 577
Głogów	:	500	:	200	:	:	:	786
Kędzierzyn-Koźle	17 340	904	2 664	50 090	51 170	28 895	17 010	3 787
Kostrzyn	:	:	460	:	:	:	:	:
Kraków	161 280	83 324	2 600	:	:	:	:	:
Opole	199	2 470	1 172	:	1 788	130	5 140	3 828
Płock	294	5 425	121	:	400	87	70	411
Sandomierz	13 538	37 490	16 380	:	10 800	:	:	:
Wrocław	5 103 433	1 899 886	2 480 168	2 612 746	2 718 942	2 458 693	2 284 422	422 541

Source: GUS, Eurostat

The determination of transportation routes in inland waterway transport is influenced by the spatial distribution of principal shipping and receiving points adjacent to the waterway, alongside prevailing navigational conditions. These factors significantly affect the spatial scope of transport operations. Based on these considerations, the following classifications of transport routes in inland waterway transport can be identified:

- **Long-Distance Routes:** These routes involve transport over segments of the waterway that extend through at least three voivodeships (provinces).
- **Regional Routes:** These routes involve transport with loading and unloading points situated within two adjacent voivodeships.
- **Local Routes:** These routes involve transport with loading and unloading points confined within a single voivodeship.

The presence of numerous locations with limited transit depths on Poland's inland waterways restricts the feasibility of long-distance transport operations. This limitation currently affects even the premier inland waterway in Poland, the Oder Waterway, which comprises the Oder River (length 733.7 km), the Gliwice Canal (length 41.2 km), and the Kędzierzyn Canal (length 5.9 km).

Greater opportunities exist for the execution of regional and local transport routes. At present, such operations are conducted on:

- The Canalized Oder River (Koźle – Malczyce, length approximately 200 km): Particularly between Koźle and Wrocław.
- The Lower Oder River between Kostrzyn and Szczecin (length 33 km).

The Gliwice Canal, despite its nominal transit depth of 1.8 meters (transit depths are effectively reduced due to silting between the Gliwice Port and the Łabędy lock), performs a limited transport function. Similarly, the navigational utility of the Kędzierzyn Canal is constrained, with vessel movement feasible only along the central axis of the canal and requiring heightened caution. The central section of the Oder River, from the Malczyce lock to the confluence with the Warta River (321.65 km), has diminished in transport utility due to significantly reduced depths, often falling below 1 meter. In July 2022, transit depths in this section locally did not exceed 50 cm. Consequently, cargo transport on this section is infrequent or non-existent.

Long-distance transport routes on the Oder Waterway are predominantly associated with the transshipment activities at the sea ports of Szczecin-Świnoujście. In 2021, inland waterway transport accounted for 319,200 tons in servicing the ports of Szczecin and Świnoujście, representing a mere 1.1% of the total transshipments at these ports. By contrast, during the period 2005–2011, this share ranged from 6% to 11%.

Within the context of inland waterway transportation (IWT) serving the seaports at the mouth of the Oder River, freight transport can be categorized into domestic and international relations. Domestic freight transport was regularly conducted in the 1970s and 1980s from the seaports at the mouth of the Oder to Gliwice and Wrocław. The transported goods mainly included iron ore (from the ports of Szczecin and Świnoujście to Silesia) and coal (from Silesia to the ports of Szczecin and Świnoujście). From the mid-1990s, these transports gradually began to decline, and by 2012, they were practically suspended due to unstable water levels and insufficient transit depths. Currently, domestic long distance freight transports on the Oder, if conducted, are only incidental. Reflected in the current significance of inland waterway transports on the Oder are cargo volumes between loading/unloading locations in the West Pomeranian Voivodeship and loading/unloading locations in the Lower Silesian or Opole Voivodeships, as shown in official statistics. In the years 2010–2021, the volume of transports in these relations often did not exceed 1 thousand tons annually and consequently was not even included in official statistics.

Presently, long distance freight transports on the Oder are almost exclusively conducted in the east-west direction, i.e., from the seaports of Szczecin and Świnoujście to the river ports of Western Europe. These transports are primarily executed in export relations to Germany. However, overall export IWW transports exhibit a clear decreasing trend in terms of volume.

In 2021, the dominant cargo groups in IWW export relations were:

- Secondary raw materials; municipal wastes and other wastes (14.1%)
- Products of agriculture, hunting, and forestry; fish and other fishing products (37.4%)
- Coal and lignite; crude petroleum and natural gas (15.3%)
- Chemicals, chemical products, and man-made fibers; rubber and plastic products nuclear fuel (14.7%).

As mentioned, some transports related to the ports of Szczecin and Świnoujście are conducted on local routes. In Poland, a significant dependence of inland navigation operators on this type of transport was observed as early as the 1970s. Over the following years, the concentration of activity on local transports deepened further. The volume of transports on the Oder in the West Pomeranian Voivodeship from 2016 to 2022 decreased from 1,058 thousand tons to 442 thousand tons. Local transports on the lower section of the Oder are primarily associated with:

- Delivering extracted aggregates from mines belonging to the Szczecin Minerals Resources Mines Company to transshipment points in Szczecin, Świnoujście, Police, Stepnica, and Trzebież.
- Servicing port-related industries.

From 2010 to 2022, a trend of decreasing volume and share of metal ores and other mining products (including sand, gravel, and stones) in total transports on the Oder in the West Pomeranian Voivodeship was observed, from 85.6% in 2010 to 47.4% in 2022. These transports showed significant stability in terms of the average transport distance of 1 ton, which stood at 61 km.

Greater activity of inland navigation operators in this region has been noted since 2015 regarding the transport of coke and petroleum refining products (these are entirely transports of liquid petroleum refining products). From 2015 to 2022, the share of this cargo group in total transports in this region of the Oder increased from 10.9% to 50.0%. However, the average transport distance of 1 ton showed a decrease from 71.4 km in 2015 to 67.9 km in 2022.

In serving the seaports of Szczecin and Świnoujście, inland navigation also conducts so-called bridge transports. These types of transports (technological) aim to streamline the entire port complex by enabling the movement of goods between ports and quays in Szczecin, Świnoujście, and Police.

Inland navigation on the Oder in relations with the ports of Szczecin and Świnoujście is losing significance. In 2021, the share of inland waterway transport in handling transshipments in these ports was 1.1%, whereas in the 1980s, it ranged from 14% to 16%, and at the beginning of the 21st century, it was around 10%.

As previously mentioned, transports on regional and local routes are concentrated in the canalized Oder region. The most significant transportation route is mainly from the lock in Kędzierzyn-Koźle to the lock in Brzeg Dolny (281.6 km). Vessel traffic on this section of the Oder is not dependent on water levels, as with normal damming, a transit depth of 1.8 m can be maintained (this depth allows for optimal utilization of typical barges' capacities in Poland). Greater navigation challenges on the canalized Oder occur between the Brzeg Dolny lock and the Malczyce lock (300.0 km). During navigation on this section, the ship's crew must be in constant contact with operators at the Malczyce and Brzeg Dolny locks and comply with their instructions while exercising particular caution.

Cargo transports on the upper Oder waterway are primarily local in nature and mainly concentrate in the Lower Silesian Voivodeship. From 2010 to 2022, these transports exhibited considerable variability. From 2010 to 2014, they increased from 242 thousand tons to 3715 thousand tons, followed by a downward trend in the subsequent years, reaching only 210 thousand tons in 2022. These transports are carried out over increasingly shorter distances. From 2010 to 2014, the average transport distance of 1 ton of cargo by waterway in the Lower Silesian Voivodeship was 9.1 km, decreasing to 4.3 km from 2015 to 2022.

An analysis of the cargo structure of transports on the waterway in the Dolnośląskie Voivodeship indicates that these transports exclusively encompass two cargo groups:

- Coal and lignite; crude petroleum and natural gas.
- Metal ores and other mining and quarrying products; peat; uranium and thorium.

In 2022, coal transports in this region of the Oder accounted for 57.1%, while transports of metal ores and other mining products accounted for 42.9%

The Vistula waterway exhibits a significantly lesser transportation function. On this water route, both trunk transports and regional transports between neighboring provinces are rare occurrences, and if they are conducted, they lack statistical significance.

Transportation on the Vistula is almost exclusively limited to servicing local routes. As per Table 17, these transports were only conducted until 2016 in the Małopolskie Voivodeship (with an average transport distance of 22.1 km per ton) and the Świętokrzyskie Voivodeship. Transports on the Vistula in the Kujawsko-Pomorskie Voivodeship were conducted until 2018 (with an average transport distance of 2.8 km per ton). These transports exclusively involved sand and construction aggregates from local mines and from

Since 2015, some activity has been observed in inland waterway transport in the Pomeranian Voivodeship. The highest volume of transports (approximately 330 thousand tons annually) was recorded in this region in the years 2015-2016. The primary cargo group during this period comprised Metal ores and other mining and quarrying products; peat; uranium and thorium. In 2021, as well as in 2022, 7 thousand tons were transported via inland waterways in the Pomeranian Voivodeship. These transports solely involved Secondary raw materials; municipal wastes and other wastes.

Due to the dynamic development of the maritime port in Gdańsk and existing transshipment forecasts, it can be expected that there will be an increased need for transportation utilization of the lower section of the Vistula. Currently, navigational conditions on the Vistula from the Włocławek water lock to its mouth into the Gdańsk Bay allow for regular inland waterway transport only if barges are submerged within the range of 1.0–1.2 meters, a level recognized in Poland as the threshold for the profitability of waterway transport.

As mentioned earlier, inland waterway transport is particularly suited for oversized cargo transports. Currently, these transports on the Vistula are possible only under conditions of extreme caution, extensive knowledge of the water route, and significant ship crew experience. It is even recommended that during winter periods, these transports be conducted in the presence of a representative from the IWW infrastructure manager onboard the vessel.

Historical data on freight traffic on the waterway routes of the Vistula and Oder confirm the low interest in implementing inland waterways into modern transportation chains. Despite this, projections of the volume potential to be transferred to inland solutions are in line with the goals of the ongoing Cristal project. The identification of chains potentially suitable for the implementation of inland transportation, the development of recommendations for authorities and logistics operators, or, finally, the development of a system of buoys to support the transparency and flexibility of supply chains can make an important contribution to changes in transport chains.

5. Supply chain model development

A supply chain model refers to a conceptual or mathematical representation of the processes, activities, and flows that are involved in producing and delivering goods or services from suppliers to customers. It typically includes entities such as suppliers, manufacturers, distributors, retailers, and customers, and it outlines the interactions and exchanges between these entities. According to Mentzer et al. (2001): "Supply chain models are structured methodologies used to describe, analyze, and improve the supply chain by focusing on the interconnected components and processes, ranging from sourcing raw materials to delivering final products". Subject paper refers to building supply chains based on IWT. To successfully implement IWT into supply chains it is necessary to indicate deciding factors affecting on it. For most of the factors it is unfeasible to measure exact impact on IWT suitability, thus implementation on binary or point scale of suitability was changed into fluent gradation from most to less suitable.

The characteristics describing the suitability of goods for transport are referred to in the literature as transport susceptibility. Within this concept, three primary types of susceptibility can be distinguished:

- Natural Susceptibility
- Technical Susceptibility
- Economic Susceptibility

5.1. Commodity

Natural susceptibility is defined as the resistance of cargo to transport conditions, arising from the physical, chemical, and biological properties of the transported products. Consequently, some cargo types, due to their natural characteristics, are unsuitable for inland waterway transport. The following characteristics affect the suitability of cargo for inland waterway transport:

Sensitivity to Transit Time

Certain cargoes, such as perishable food products, fruits, vegetables, and live animals, require the shortest possible transport time. In such cases, the use of inland waterway transport may lead to a loss in the value of the cargo, or in extreme cases, total damage and disposal of the goods. In Poland, the average speed of an inland barge is around 10 km/h, which is half the average speed of a freight train and up to five times slower than the average speed of a truck. Therefore, for time-sensitive cargo, road transport is the optimal solution. Additionally, inland waterway transport is limited by extreme weather conditions. Sensitivity to transport time does not solely arise from the physical properties of the product itself.

Sensitivity to Moisture, Temperature, and Light

Some cargoes, such as chemical or food products, require transportation in a controlled atmosphere. Here, road transport proves efficient due to the wide availability of refrigerated vehicles. The inland waterway transport market in Poland lacks an adequate fleet for such needs. Moreover, some cargoes, like agricultural, chemical, and certain food products, lose their properties upon contact with water or excessive moisture. Such risks in inland waterway transport are mitigated by using barges with covered holds to reduce the impact of atmospheric conditions on the cargo. Alternatively, for certain cargoes, unitization and transport in containers can ensure the safety of the cargo.

Odor Release and Absorption

Such cargoes also require appropriate barges or containers that allow for safe transport. Additionally, for bulk transport, it is crucial to prevent the mixing of such cargoes within the same hold. However, these types of cargoes are not disqualified from inland waterway transport. Cargoes that emit and absorb odors primarily include biomass and grain milling products, such as rice, groats, grits, and flour.

Susceptibility to Spillage, Leakage, and Evaporation

The susceptibility of cargo to spillage or loss usually necessitates containerization or unitization (e.g., big bags, flexi-tanks). However, those characteristics do not disqualify the cargo to IWT. Using proper unitisation process or deploying closed bays

Hazardous Cargo

The transport of hazardous cargo on inland waterways is subject to regulations outlined in the international ADN agreement, to which Poland is a party. Therefore, the transport of such cargo is feasible but must comply with legal requirements. Given the limited availability of inland waterway units, the transport of hazardous cargo on the Oder and Vistula markets may remain challenging. Another factor affecting the implementation of inland waterway transport for such goods is the possibility of transshipment and storage of hazardous materials in active ports and wharves in Poland, which limitations has been outlined in previous chapter.

All other cargoes with characteristics not listed above can be classified as F.A.K. (Freight All Kinds), which are generally not subject to restrictions in inland waterway transport.

Based on the analysis of cargo susceptibility to inland waterway transport, a scale of suitability for inland waterway navigation has been developed. Depending on the characteristics, cargo can be classified as suitable for inland waterway navigation, suitable under the condition of additional verification (availability of equipment, crew training, proper cargo packaging), or unsuitable for inland waterway navigation (Table 12).

Table 12 *Commodity type and its' influence on IWT suitability*

Commodity characteristics	Suitability for IWT
NEUTRAL F.A.K.	SUITABLE FOR IWT
DANGEROUS GOODS	NEED ADDITIONAL VERIFICATION
HUMIDITY SENSITIVE	NEED ADDITIONAL VERIFICATION
ODOR RELEASE AND ABSORPTION	NEED ADDITIONAL VERIFICATION
TIME SENSITIVE	NOT SUITABLE FOR IWT
TEMPERATURE CONTROL	NOT SUITABLE FOR IWT

Source: Own Elaboration

5.2. Cargo Characteristics

Technical susceptibility refers to how cargo is packaged and prepared for transport, significantly influencing its suitability for various transport modes, including inland waterways. Proper packaging enhances the safety and efficiency of the transport process.

Bulk cargo, such as grains, coal, and ores, is highly suitable for inland waterway transport. The available barges on the Vistula and Oder rivers are designed to handle large quantities of bulk materials efficiently, making this type of cargo ideal for such transport. Similarly, unitized general cargo, which includes goods packaged into standardized units like pallets or containers, also demonstrates high suitability for inland waterway transport. This method of packaging allows for easier handling, loading, and unloading, enhancing the overall efficiency of the transport process. Additionally, the versatility of the available barges enables them to transport containers effectively. Containerization provides numerous benefits, including improved cargo protection, easier handling, and the ability to stack and store cargo efficiently. Heavy cargo units exceeding 12 tons per twenty-foot equivalent unit (TEU) are particularly suitable for inland waterway transport. These heavy units benefit from better utilization of the vessel's available tonnage, making it a cost-effective alternative to road transport, which often faces weight limitations and regulatory constraints.

However, there are limitations to inland waterway transport. Poland lacks inland waterway vessels specifically designed for transporting liquid or gaseous cargo, such as tankers or gas carriers. Consequently, it is currently not feasible to transport such cargo via inland waterways in Poland. While it is possible to unitize liquid or gaseous cargo into tank containers or flexi-tanks for inland waterway transport, the associated costs can be prohibitively high. This increased cost may render the operation economically unfeasible, limiting the practicality of this transport method. Furthermore, the absence of specialized units and transshipment points for rolling cargo, such as vehicles and machinery, effectively eliminates the possibility of inland waterway transport for these types of cargo in Poland. This limitation necessitates the use of alternative transport modes, such as road or rail.

Oversized cargo, including large industrial components and heavy machinery, naturally moves towards inland waterway transport due to its unique dimensions and weight. These cargoes often exceed the permissible size and weight limits for road and rail transport, making waterway transport a practical and necessary alternative. The selection and preparation of road transport routes for oversized units, such as project cargo, can be complex and costly. This includes obtaining necessary permits, arranging pilot vehicles, and ensuring infrastructure compatibility. Inland waterway transport can bypass many of these challenges, offering a more straightforward and cost-effective solution. Thus, inland waterway transport often becomes the preferred choice for oversized cargo due to its cost efficiency. The ability to transport large and heavy items without the need for extensive route modifications and regulatory compliance makes it a natural choice for shippers looking to optimize their logistics operations.

Table 13 IWT cargo suitability depending on cargo type

Cargo Type	Suitability for IWT
Project Cargo	MOST SUITABLE
Bulk	
General Cargo	
Containerised	
Liquid	
Gas	
Ro-Ro	LESS SUITABLE

Source: Own Elaboration

5.3. Incoterms

Incoterms, or International Commercial Terms, are a fundamental element in global trade and logistics, establishing clear rules for the interpretation of the most commonly used trade terms. Developed by the International Chamber of Commerce (ICC), Incoterms define the obligations, costs, and risks associated with the delivery of goods from the seller to the buyer, playing a key role in sales contracts. Incoterms impact crucial aspects of commercial transactions, including the delivery of goods, insurance, customs clearance, and other formalities. Over the decades, Incoterms have been updated to reflect changing practices and needs in international trade. The latest version, Incoterms 2020, introduces precise guidelines aimed at facilitating trade worldwide.

Understanding Incoterms is essential for all parties involved in the international supply chain, from manufacturers and exporters to importers and freight forwarders. Incoterms specify the point at which responsibility for the goods transfers from the seller to the buyer, which has significant implications for both the costs and risks associated with the transportation of goods. The classification of Incoterms divides them into groups, such as E (Ex Works), F (Free On Board), C and D, each offering different levels of obligations for sellers and buyers.

Implementing Incoterms in business practice requires an understanding of the specifics of the transaction and a conscious choice of the most appropriate terms. Choosing the right Incoterms is crucial for optimizing costs, managing risk, and logistical efficiency. These terms affect the choice of transport method, supply chain planning, pricing strategies, and insurance strategies. Therefore, a thorough analysis and appropriate application of Incoterms in trade and logistics contracts can contribute to increasing companies' competitiveness in the international market.

The terms of delivery according to Incoterms do not directly affect the possibility or method of transportation but primarily determine the responsibility for shaping the logistics chain. Due to the low prevalence of inland waterway transport in logistics chains in Poland, it should be assumed that leaving the transport responsibility to the importer or exporter from Poland allows for better decision-making regarding the shape of the logistics chain within the country. This is particularly important for containerized cargo. Modern logistics chains for such cargo are largely shaped by global logistics companies or even ocean shipping lines. The global scale of their operations necessitates the standardization of processes, which can hinder the shift of cargo from default transportation modes (road, less frequently rail) to inland waterway transport. Leaving the transport responsibility to the Polish shipper or consignee allows, in cooperation with the freight forwarder, for the implementation of a logistics model based on inland waterway transport. Therefore, depending on the direction of transport, for import cargo, delivery terms from groups C, F, and E are more suitable for implementing inland waterway transport. For export cargo, conditions from groups F, C, and D are more favorable. The development of supply chains based on inland waterway transport for containerized cargo is further complicated by the issue of managing empty containers, which are usually the property of the ocean carrier. If the party entering into the maritime container transport contract does not take into account the specifics of subsequent supply chain elements and, for example, does not agree on additional free time for the consignee's use of the container or does not include the possibility of returning the empty container to the carrier at inland terminals, the implementation of inland waterway transport may prove impossible or generate additional costs, impacting the economic efficiency of the transport.

IMPORT	INCOTERMS	EXPORT
<p>MOST SUITABLE</p> <p>LESS SUITABLE</p>	<p>EXW</p> <p>FCA</p> <p>FAS</p> <p>FOB</p> <p>CPT</p> <p>CIP</p> <p>CFR</p> <p>CIF</p> <p>DPU</p> <p>DAP</p> <p>DDP</p>	<p>LESS SUITABLE</p> <p>MOST SUITABLE</p>

Figure 5 Corolation between INCOTERMS and shipment suitability to IWT

Source: Own Elaboration

It is worth noting that it is estimated that over one-third of Polish exports by value are sold under EXW and FCA terms, which are less suitable for evolving supply chains into inland waterway transport (IWT), mainly due to the limited willingness of export companies to engage in additional work. For IWT, this means that the transition process and securing the proper volume to develop the IWT market in Poland may require additional efforts to shift international trade to more suitable Incoterms formulas. An even higher share of less suitable terms can be observed in import shipments. Estimates show that over 40% of import contracts are signed under DAP and DDP terms. Among many reasons, it is worth highlighting that most corporations involved in international trade, which have branches in Poland, require their suppliers to use DAP terms, affecting the total share of DAP and DDP terms in the mix of all contracts delivered to Poland. Additionally, the current market situation shows significant uncertainty and risk avoidance, so recent research indicates a greater share of Incoterms with less involvement and risk on the part of Polish importers/exporters.

Figure 6 Estimated share of INCOTERMS in Polish Export and Import in terms of value

Source: Own Elaboration

5.4. Cargo volume and frequency

Cargo volume and barge space utilisation naturally affects on unit cost of transportation. Additionally, frequency and regularity of cargo batches generated by supply chain allows to improve barge employment/idle time factor, which also may lead to total costs decrease. Another factor is market demand, which allows to secure backhaul cargo for barge. Such factors will lead the market to increase the competition and decrease the costs of barge deployment. Lower rates allow to better compete with road solutions, and catch the attention of cargo owners and freight forwarders.

Research showed, that at current market development, barge skippers are keen to decrease the costs of barge deployment up to 50% in case of contracting backhaul cargo. Such decrease may led the market to become comparable to road transportation costs and much positive market attitude to IWW solutions

Figure 7 Estimated costs of transporting 1T of loose cargo

Source: Own Elaboration

5.5. Last mile distance

In transport chains based on inland waterway transport (IWT), costs can be divided into those related to inland waterway transport operations, transshipment and terminal handling, and land delivery to/from the consignee's or shipper's premises. Last-mile delivery costs, often comprising more than 30% of the total transport costs, are particularly significant. Therefore, the distance from the delivery point to the terminal servicing the logistics chain is crucial for achieving economic efficiency in the chain and thus for implementing IWT as a permanent solution for specific cargo groups.

Based on the estimated transport costs for routes planned within the framework of pilot voyages on the Vistula River, and the road transport costs for analogous routes, road transport costs were established as

the upper limit of acceptable costs. The difference between the cost of inland waterway transport and road transport should cover the transshipment and last-mile delivery costs. Consequently, the type of cargo being transported also limits the acceptable delivery distance. The highest transshipment costs, according to available terminal tariffs, concern unitized general cargo (such as big bags, bundles, and pallets). The primary reason is the need for appropriate handling equipment—spreaders, straps, or grips—which affects the time required for transshipment operations. The second group consists of bulk loose cargo. The cheapest cargo to handle at the terminal, mainly due to the high degree of process automation, and unification of unit size is containerized cargo.

It should be noted that the optimal distance from the loading/delivery point to the terminal may vary across different local transport markets. The primary factor extending the acceptable distance from the terminal is the cost of inland waterway transport, driven by demand and supply in the open shipping market. The second factor is the availability of road transport means and competition in that market. Therefore, it is impossible to definitively determine the upper limit of the influence range of an inland waterway terminal. For simplification, an average distance of 50 km has been adopted in the model, although cost estimates for pilot voyages indicate that the upper cost limit is exceeded for certain cargo groups at this distance (figures below).

Figure 8 Estimated transportation costs for general cargo [per ton]

Source: Own Elaboration

Figure 9 Estimated transportation costs for containerised cargo [per ton]

Source: Own Elaboration

Figure 10 Estimated transportation costs for bulk cargo [per ton]

Source: Own Elaboration

5.6. Cargo value

The value of the cargo is a determining factor for its economic transportability, which classifies cargoes into low-value, medium-value, and high-value categories, thereby influencing the choice of transportation technology due to the varying scope of requirements.

The economic transport susceptibility of cargo is defined as the cargo's resilience to the conditions and effects of transportation, determined by the ratio of transportation costs to the value of the transported cargo. In other words, the economic transport susceptibility of cargo is the ratio of freight charges and other transportation-related expenses to the value of the transported cargo.

The lower the share of transportation costs in the cargo's value, the higher its economic susceptibility to carriage. Conversely, the higher the value of the cargo, the lower its economic susceptibility, as it necessitates more meticulous care during transportation.

Higher-value transported products concurrently increase the potential for choosing among various transportation branches and modes, as they accommodate transport options characterized by higher delivery costs. Additionally, the economic transportability of cargo is influenced by the possibility of reducing delivery times, which can lead to a reduction in the cost of capital tied up in the transported cargo, thereby increasing the capital turnover rate.

Low-value cargo

Low – value cargo has a high natural susceptibility to transport, does not require special care from the carrier, and can be transported using the simplest means. These cargoes are typically not time-sensitive and seek the lowest share of transportation and logistics costs in the total goods price. Consequently, such goods are usually most suitable for inland waterways. Examples include most bulk products, scrap, or non-unitized grain.

Medium-value cargo

Medium–value cargo exhibits different technical transport susceptibilities, necessitating adherence to specific transport technologies during carriage.

High-value cargo

High-value cargo is often associated with the FMCG market or comprises high-tech products, electronic devices, special machinery, or certain automotive parts. These high-value products require additional escort or special convoy procedures and are primarily transported by road, in containers, or hard-body semitrailers.

Below table provide a range of goods commonly freighted by IWW. Based on average value of the cargo (market prices) and fixed transportation costs a percentage share of costs in cargo value has been indicated. Calculated shares confirm, that lower value cargo naturally gravitate towards inland waterways transport.

Table 14 *Transport costs share in cargo value for selected commodities*

CARGO TYPE	TRANSPORT COSTS SHARE IN CARGO VALUE
METAL SCRAP	5,26%
COAL	4,82%
WHEAT GRAIN	3,96%
UNITIZED FETILIZER (BIG BAGS)	2,97%
LADEN CONTAINERS (1 LAYER)	1,35%
LADEN CONTAINERS (2 LAYERS)	0,67%

Source: Own Elaboration

Oversized cargo

A completely different aspect is the transport of oversized cargo, particularly investment cargo such as Project Cargo. Despite the high value of such cargo, due to its technical parameters, the use of inland waterway transport is often the only viable option for moving the product. In these cases, the inclination towards inland waterway transport is solely due to the physical characteristics of the cargo, excluding an analysis of its economic transportability.

An analysis of the cargo potential transshipped in the ports of the Tri-City area (Gdańsk, Gdynia) and Szczecin, which are the main generators of cargo flows in inland navigation, confirms a significant stream of cargo potentially inclined towards inland waterway transport. Both in the ports of Gdańsk and Gdynia and in Szczecin/Świnoujście, substantial quantities of bulk cargo (such as coal, ores, and grain) are transshipped, with the possibility of further transshipment onto inland barges (see figure below).

Figure 11 Cargo turnovers in Polish ports

Source: Own Elaboration

Conducted research showed, a set of existing factors that describe individual transportation chains. The values that each factor takes affect the feasibility of implementing IWT into a supply chain. Measuring and quantifying all the factors, however, is not possible and their interpretation does not always unequivocally accept or reject cargo for transportation using IWT. Nevertheless, ranking them according to the scale of impact makes it possible to determine which chains are more, or less, suitable for implementing new shipping solutions. In practice, it is only through a thorough analysis of the concrete supply chain that its potential for IWT implementation can be determined.

6. Pilot Specification

Wide variety of goods available for IWW transportation and specific supply chain configurations requires to perform a number of voyages to investigate the influence of introducing IWW into real supply chains.

The primary objective of the pilot is to integrate Inland Waterway Transport (IWW) into a diverse array of supply chains with various cargo types to promote modal shift. These new supply chains will necessitate a modern approach regarding flexibility and traceability. Consequently, the pilot voyages will include tests of the intelligent buoy system developed by L-PIT. This smart buoy system will further support logistics operators in the decision-making process for optimizing supply chains under extreme navigational conditions.

A comprehensive range of cargo types that can be transported and integrated into logistics chains necessitates the execution of four separate pilot voyages. Based on the conducted desk research, the following groups of cargo have been selected for test transportation:

- Conventional general cargo
- Containerized cargo
- Dry bulk cargo (dry)

Additionally, due to the specific nature of navigation in Polish geography, two waterway routes have been identified for the pilot voyages:

- The E40 International Waterway, on the Vistula River
- The E30 International Waterway, on the Oder River

The scope of research during these voyages and the expected outcomes have been tailored to the current navigational conditions and the operational dynamics of the transport market on the specified routes. Given the navigational conditions and the availability of the waterways, the voyages are scheduled to be conducted in the third quarter of 2024. During summer (May-August) IWW remaining mostly unavailable for freight traffic, due to low water levels. At the end of June 2024 Vistula river water level showed 1,85m in Torun and 0,87m in Malczyce for Odra waterway. Barge deployed for voyages requires at least 1,8m to pass the waterways with holds fully laden. Thus, pilot operator decided to re-schedule pilot operations till September – October, when water level rise above required levels. Pilots to be conducted on the existing supply chain, which are under influence of many factors, including commercial, operational and political. Thus, all elements of the pilot may affect changes and disruptions in short notice.

6.1. Pilot site

Pilot I, II General Cargo, Containerised cargo

The selected logistics operator for the pilot voyages confirmed the lower Vistula River as the site for execution during technical discussions. The voyage involves transporting empty containers from an inland port in Gdańsk along the E40 waterway south to Włocławek. After loading the empty containers, the barge returns to Gdańsk, where the containers will be offloaded at the quay and subsequently loaded onto an ocean-going vessel. In the next voyage, general cargo will also be transported from a quay in Włocławek to the maritime port in Gdańsk. From Gdańsk, the cargo will continue its maritime journey to the final

recipient. The total IWW transport distance for each pilot is approximately 280 km one way, with a planned transit time one way approximately 72 hours, including restrictions on night navigation.

The route features one lock and 15 bridges. The Przegalina Lock allows barges to enter the Vistula from the Dead Vistula, a natural connector to the seaport in Gdańsk. The lock is 188 meters long and 11.9 meters wide. During the navigable season for barges (spring, autumn), lock operations are available from 7 AM to 7 PM, Monday to Friday, and on weekends with prior notification.

Several bridges along the route from Gdańsk to the unloading quay in Włocławek significantly impact the barge's maximum load capacity, especially for voyages with containerized cargo. As indicated in the table below, some structures may restrict the possibility of stacking containers in two tiers.

Table 15 *Bridges over pilots site on Vistula river*

Bridge	Location	GPS	Min. clearance
Siennicki Bridge	Gdansk	54.355094, 18.677284	6,4m
Rail Bridge	Gdansk	54.35602, 18.69177	8,0m
Cable Bridge	Gdansk	54.35668, 18.69405	9,0m
Sobieszewo Bridge	Gdansk	54.34238, 18.82471	5,0m, movable
Kiezmark old Bridge	Kiezmark	54.25671, 18.94677	6,79m
Tczew Rail Bridge	Tczew	54.09264, 18.80617	7,0m
Knybawski Bridge	Baldowo	54.05181, 18.81534	8,0m
Korzeniewo Bridge	Korzeniewo	53.75939, 18.84767	12m
Malinowski Bridge	Grudziadz	53.48382, 18.74035	5,28m
Motorway bridge	Grudziadz	53.44161, 18.68144	7,0m
Chelmno bridge	Chelmno	53.36937, 18.42804	7,5m
Fordon bridge	Bydgoszcz	53.14383, 18.17189	5,5m
Road bridge	Torun	53.00499, 18.60195	5,17m
Rail bridge	Torun	53.01501, 18.65494	9,44m
Motorway bridge	Torun	52.97285, 18.7005	11,2

Source: own elaboration

Pilot III Bulk Cargo

The third pilot involves the transport of bulk scrap steel cargo in an export voyage. The planned routing, similar to the first two pilot runs, will take place on the E40 waterway along the lower Vistula. However, due to the location of the exporting facilities cargo handling will take place in old port in Plock (70km farther south, down the Vistula river). After sailing approximately 350 km downstream, the cargo will be delivered to the exporter's bulk quay at the port of Gdańsk, where goods will be reloaded to an oceangoing vessel to the Middle East.

Below map shows the routing for all three Vistula voyages, red path indicates pilots I and II, green shows routing selected for bulk cargo.

Figure 12 Vistula river pilots route Red path – Pilot I II, Green path – Pilot III

Source: Own elaboration based on UNCECE ADN network map.

Pilot IV Containerised cargo on international waterway

Due to the pilot's focus on enhancing the importance and potential of inland navigation in Poland, the pilot project is geographically focused on inland navigation along the Polish section of the international waterway. The primary objective of the fourth pilot is to investigate the capability of inland navigation to compete with alternative transportation modes such as rail and road transport. Therefore, for this pilot voyage, the route selected is between the Upper Silesia region and Antwerp, one of the major container hubs in Europe. A regular intermodal train service operated between Gliwice and Antwerp by one of the intermodal operators will serve as a reference and comparison.

The journey will commence by loading laden and empty containers at the terminal in the Port of Antwerp. After passing through Netherlands and Germany Mittelland Kanal, the barge will enter the Oder River via the Oder-Spree Canal. Oder river is divided into two parts. First part, from Oder-Spree Canal entrance to Brzeg Dolny lock is free flowing river, according to UNECE with II class of navigability. Second part of the

river is called canalised Oder and connects Brzeg Dolny lock with port of Kozle which can be considered as gateway to industrial region of Silesia.

The canalized Odra River features 24 locks, with 23 currently used for navigation. This section, from Brzeg Dolny to Kedzierzyn Kozle, spans 187.1 km, with distances between the weirs ranging from 4 to 21 km. The total elevation drop across all weirs is approximately 65.0 m, varying from 1.75 m at Chróścice to 6.70 m at Brzeg Dolny. Each weir includes a dam and locks. From the Januszkowice lock (the first major lock downstream from Koźle) to the Różanka lock in Wrocław, the locks are 9.6 m wide, except for Zwanowice and Janowice, which are 12 m wide. The Rędzin and Brzeg Dolny locks also measure 12 m in width.

Table 16 Locks along chanalized Oder waterway

Lock	Length	Width	GPS
Januszkowice	187	9,6	50.39002, 18.11137
Krępna	187	9,6	50.42715, 18.06679
Krapkowice	198	9,6	50.46975, 17.99006
Rogów	187	9,6	50.51074, 17.94819
Kąty	187	9,6	50.56366, 17.96934
Groszowice	186,9	9,6	50.62215, 17.95685
Opole	187,4	9,6	50.65762, 17.92363
Wróblin	187,1	9,6	50.71215, 17.8888
Dobrzeń	187,1	9,6	50.75492, 17.83343
Chróścice	187,1	9,6	50.76031, 17.78752
Zawada	187,1	9,6	50.79128, 17.72052
Ujście Nysy	187,2	9,6	50.8165, 17.66188
Zwanowice	190	12	50.82742, 17.5929
Brzeg	187,2	9,6	50.86216, 17.48651
Lipki	187,3	9,6	50.9154, 17.4086
Oława	187	9,6	50.9408, 17.31468
Ratowice	187	9,6	51.03282, 17.25589
Janowice	225	12	51.05294, 17.20582
Bartoszwice	187,8	9,6	51.10343, 17.12573
Zacisze	187,8	9,6	51.12893, 17.07995
Różanka	196,2	9,6	51.13292, 17.02445
Rędzin	226	12	51.15799, 16.96334
Brzeg Dolny	224,9	12	51.25821, 16.76253

Source: Own elaboration

After traveling approximately 450 kilometers, on polish part of waterway, passing through mentioned locks and bridges barge with berth at the transshipment quay in Koźle. From there, containers will be transported within the first/last mile by road up to 150km as crow flies to actual consignees and shippers and then

returned back to Kozle. Furtherly, units will be laden on board the barge, will return using the same inland waterway route back to Antwerp.

Figure 13 Oder river pilot route

Source: Own elaboration based on UNCECE ADN network map.

6.2. Type of cargo

Pilot I: General Cargo

Conventional general cargo refers to individual units of cargo transported by conventional means aboard liners in a traditional manner. This includes goods transported in bags, barrels, crates, pallets, beams, and boxes, but may also include other untized cargo such as wire bundles or steel coils. An analysis of potential flows for transporting conventional general cargo in the lower Vistula region identified the potential for transporting bulk cargo consolidated into big bags.

The pilot transport project will involve approximately 900 big bags of chemical products for agricultural and manufacturing purposes, with an estimated gross cargo between 720-750 tons. Commodity and its suitability has been previously verified using developed suitability factor (table 16.). Currently, supply chain is served with regular rail connection between factory's railway siding and terminal Fosfory in Port of Gdansk.

Table 17 General cargo - IWT suitability model

Commodity characteristics	General cargo
NEUTRAL F.A.K.	YES
DANGEROUS GOODS	NO
HUMIDITY SENSITIVE	Partially, require closed holds during voyage
ODOR RELEASE AND ABSORPTION	NO

TIME SENSITIVE	NO
TEMPERATURE CONTROL	NO

Source: own elaboration

Pilot II, IV: Containerized Cargo

Containerization and standardization of general cargo allow for combining different type of FAK goods and transport during a single voyage. In this case, the logistics operator's role involves consolidating containers and ensuring proper utilization of the barge's cargo space. However, for the pilot II voyage, the entire containerized cargo will consist of containers carrying chemical products from chemical plant, which manage the quayside in Włocławek. According to the cargo owner's shipping plans, total number of containers may vary depending on actual demand and ordered batch quantity. Based on historical data, average batch consist of 12x40' containers. For better container capacity utilisation, logisitcs operator expects to load 26tons of goods per container, which is not possible to achieve using road transport due to infrasturcutre limitations (maximum truck gross weight). Currently, supply chain is served by railway connection in two modes: block train mode – if the batch rise up to 40x40' containers, or with use of intermodal terminal in Kutno, where operator's regular shuttle departs everyday to port od Gdansk.

The framework for the IV pilot voyage involves a significantly more complex supply chain. The voyage operator plans to consolidate cargo from various owners, akin to an intermodal operator running a train shuttle on a similar route. This approach allows the barge to transport diverse commodities suitable for inland waterway operations, though the final composition of commodities will only be determined two days before the barge's departure. The most probable products for transportation inside containers include steel coils, chemical industry products, or automotive spare parts. The voyage operator anticipates maximizing the barge's capacity with up to 12x45'PW containers. Currently selected cargo is transported by trucks, or using mentioned intermodal operator's train regularly launched between Gliwice and Antwerp.

Pilot III: Dry bulk goods

Due to their natural characteristics such as high gross weight and relatively low value (typically industrial raw materials), dry bulk cargoes are naturally suitable for inland waterway transport. This is evident in the case of the third pilot project, where the cargo of choice is steel scrap. Implementation of this cargo to developed model confirmed its suitability to IWW operations as non time-sensitive and low-value bulk, freight all kinds. Supply chain which become a framework of the pilot is currently operated by road traffic. Shipper loads weekly approximately 40-50 tipper trucks from Plock area to Gdansk port. Modal shift performed during one voyage will allow to move approximately 500tons of cargo from roads to inland waterways. Such quantity of shredded scrap shall full the holds of deployed barge in terms of volume. In this case, voyage operator agreed different business model. It is shippers's responsibility to selec the quays and arrange barge loading/discharging location with first mile.

Table 18 Bulk cargo - IWT suitability model

Commodity characteristics	Bulk cargo
NEUTRAL F.A.K.	YES
DANGEROUS GOODS	NO

HUMIDITY SENSITIVE	NO
ODOR RELEASE AND ABSORPTION	NO
TIME SENSITIVE	NO
TEMPERATURE CONTROL	NO

Source: own elaboration

6.3. Equipment and technology

Barge

For the pilot voyages on the Vistula and Oder, the operator deployed the barge "Andromeda". This motorized unit measures 67 meters in total length and 7.2 meters in width. The "Andromeda" has a designed payload capacity of 749 tonnes with a draft of approximately 2.5 meters. It features a covered cargo hold measuring 45x5.45 meters, allowing for the transport of up to 14 TEU (Twenty-foot Equivalent Units) in a single layer. Unit is registered under mmsi number 261182810. Barge works on main engine MWM 400Hp in auxiliary engine DAF 190Hp and is mostly deployed on NL-DE-PL traffic. For communication with buoys, barge will be additionally equipped with signal transmitter.

Figure 14 Deployed barge - *Andromeda*

Source: Żegluga na Odrze.

Smart buoys system

The system consists of intelligent river buoys, sensors placed on bridges and transmitters placed on vessels. It will provide shipowners and managers of shipping routes with important and previously unavailable information regarding the condition of the route such as:

- bridge clearance
- strength of the river current
- river depth
- deviation of the buoy from the vertical
- GPS location of the buoy
- water temperature

Data will be useful for making certain important decisions regarding the organization of the flow of cargo. In long run it will help improve the fleet management of shipping companies.

In addition, the buoys, through wireless and automated communication with units moving along the shipping route, will provide data on the timeliness of transports or the size of possible delays or accelerations, which is a key information for effective and dynamic traffic management on the route in real time, and for more effective management of the operation of transshipment ports. For full compliance with the standards applicable in inland navigation, devices communicating wirelessly in the AIS/ATON NMEA standard were used.

The buoys are the central part of the system - they collect information on conditions of the route - water level, strength of current, temperature and bridge clearance (through wireless communication with a distance sensor on the bridge). They also identify the presence of units at a given place and time and transmit all this information to the system to be processed and made available to system users.

Mechanical development

The buoy prototypes were developed on the basis of active lighting navigation buoys, with a diameter of 700 mm, commonly used to mark shipping lanes in the test area. They have been modified to be equipped with electronic components and a replaceable power source. Adapting of existing solution allowed us to develop a functional prototype without straining the budget and schedule. Figure 1 shows chosen buoy models.

Figure 15 *Buoys chosen to be used for the solution*

Source: L-PIT own study

Figure 16 *Buoys during modification in L-PIT workshop*

Source: L-PIT own study

As part of the prototyping work, a hermetically sealed navigation buoy insert was developed. This insert securely houses communication electronics, data pre-processing devices, and battery power components, ensuring they remain safe and waterproof. Additionally, the insert simplifies maintenance tasks such as battery charging and electronics replacement. During the development process, it was determined that the optimal location for the insert is the vertical pole of the buoy. Below, an image shows the insert and its placement within the buoy.

Separately, a multisensor is embedded in the bottom of the navigation buoy, below the waterline, to measure the river depth at the buoy's anchor point and the water temperature. It also measures the velocity of the near-surface layer of the river current and the angle of deviation of the buoy from the vertical. The multisensor is connected to the previously described hermetic section via a cable and sealed connector.

Electronic development

The buoy is powered by a high-performance NERBO NBC battery, specifically designed to provide a reliable and long-lasting power source. This battery boasts a capacity of 12 volts and 24 ampere-hours, ensuring a substantial amount of energy storage.

PCB Design

The main element of the buoy prototype is a printed circuit board (PCB) consisting of a microcontroller, GSM/GPS module, SD card module, and various peripherals used to connect buoy sensors. Three DC-DC power converters (12V, 5V, and 3.3V) ensure sufficient power delivery to each component of the PCB. The microcontroller used in this prototype is the STM32L476 from ST. It is an Arm®-based 32-bit Cortex®-M4 CPU with FPU, capable of operating at a maximum frequency of 80 MHz, and has 1 MB of Flash memory. These features provide excellent performance, making it well-suited for this prototype. The GSM/GPS module used is the SARAR422M8S, which transmits all information from the buoy, including sensor

measurements and bridge clearance measurements from the bridge device. The SD card module supports microSD memory cards, storing configuration data, records of measurement activities, and the status of the instrument throughout the buoy's lifetime. The buoy supports several communication protocols, including CAN bus, RS485, RS-232, and IO-Link.

Sensors

The Multisensor DST810 Smart™ with Gen2 Paddlewheel is a cutting-edge device that combines advanced sensor technology with a highly efficient paddlewheel design. This device provides accurate, real-time measurements for various fluid flow applications.

Equipped with multiple sensors, the DST810 Smart™ measures the flow rate, temperature, and pressure of the fluid. This comprehensive data collection enables a more detailed and precise understanding of fluid dynamics.

Firmware

Firmware development started from writing down necessary features of the device. It was identified that solution should: monitor water parameters, detect nearby ships, collect data on bridge status and send all these information to the server. Based on these assumptions application state machine was written, 9.

Figure 17 State machine of the buoy

Source: L-PIT own study

The device starts by initializing all peripherals. During this step, it reads the configuration from the SD card, setting up the measurement period, server communication parameters, and working hours. After initialization, the device enters an idle state, waiting for the scheduled time to perform operations.

When the scheduled time arrives, the device begins measuring environmental parameters. Simultaneously, the AIS receiver is powered on. The device collects data on water temperature, current velocity, and buoy vertical deviation, while also listening for radio transmissions from ships and bridge stations.

Before returning to the idle state, the data is processed and stored. At the designated time, all stored data is sent to the MQTT broker. The data frames are parsed into JSON objects, examples of which are listed below.

The next task on buoy development is to configure a schedule for when the buoy should be active. This feature is essential to prolong the life of the solution in environments where recharging the battery is not possible.

Bridge station

The bridge station is a supplementary part of the system designed to support the buoy's operation. Its main goal is to monitor the clearance under the bridge and periodically send readings to the nearby buoy. By using the AIS standard for communication, all nearby river vessels can benefit from this device by obtaining real-time data on bridge clearance.

Mechanical development

For assembling the section containing the ATON and enabling radar measurement of bridge clearance, a gravity-ventilated metal cabinet was adapted. It is securely fixed to the bridge elements using non-invasive metal brackets, avoiding the need for perforations.

Electronics

The bridge sensor is powered by a high-performance NERBO NBC battery, specifically designed to provide a reliable and long-lasting power source, the exact same model as used in the buoy. This battery boasts a capacity of 12 volts and 24 ampere-hours, ensuring a substantial amount of energy storage.

PCB Design

The primary component of the bridge station prototype is a printed circuit board (PCB) incorporating a microcontroller, SD card module, and various peripherals for connecting the radar sensor and ATON transponder. To power each component effectively, three DC-DC power converters (12V, 5V, and 3.3V) were employed. The microcontroller selected for this prototype is the STM32L476 from ST, featuring an Arm®-based 32-bit Cortex®-M4 CPU with FPU capable of operating at up to 80 MHz. It includes 1 MB of Flash memory, providing optimal performance for the application. The SD card module supports microSD memory cards, storing configuration data and maintaining records of measurement activities and instrument status throughout the lifetime of the bridge station. The bridge station supports multiple communication protocols, including CAN bus, RS485, RS-232, and IO-Link. For this setup, IO-Link is utilized for communication with the radar sensor, while RS-232 is used for communication with the AIS ATON transponder.

Sensors

The radar sensor is housed in steel cuboid housings mounted non-invasively on bridges and powered by batteries during the pilot stage. Its function is to measure the actual clearance of the bridge, specifically the distance from its lowest point to the water surface, and transmit this information to the buoy via the AIS system.

Firmware

The bridge station algorithm initiates with system initialization, where the device reads configuration data from the SD card and identifies itself as a bridge station. Following power initialization (activating the 12V and 5V converters), it enters the IDLE state with all peripherals turned off.

Upon reaching the predefined measurement period, the station transitions to the MAKE_MEAS state to begin clearance measurements. Once a valid clearance value is obtained, it is transmitted via RS-232 to the AToN transponder and broadcasted using the AIS radio communication protocol. For AIS messaging, the station utilizes a custom MEB sentence (referenced at the end of this report).

Following this stage, the station enters sleep mode. Periodically, it updates its internal clock based on stored time information.

Figure 18 State machine of bridge application

Source: L-PIT own study

Automatic Identification System (AIS)

AIS (Automatic Identification System) is a technology used in maritime navigation. This system allows for the automatic transmission of information about vessels, such as position, course, speed, identifier, and other important navigational data. AIS uses radio waves to transmit this information, enabling it to be received by other ships and coastal stations within range.

Main Uses of AIS:

- **Enhancing Maritime Safety:** AIS helps ships avoid collisions by providing real-time information about the positions of nearby vessels.
- **Maritime Traffic Control:** Coastal stations and maritime traffic control centers can monitor and manage ship movements, which is especially important in high-traffic areas.
- **Search and Rescue (SAR):** AIS allows for the quick localization of ships in emergency situations, facilitating rescue operations.
- **Fleet Management:** Ship owners and operators can monitor their vessels, enabling route optimization and better operational planning.
- **Environmental Protection:** Monitoring ship movements can help protect sensitive marine areas by regulating access to these zones.

AIS is mandatory for most international ships, including cargo ships over 300 tons and all passenger ships. This system is invaluable in improving maritime safety and the efficiency of maritime traffic management.

AIS devices and equipment in bouys system

AtoN Type 3 (bridge)

Type 3 AIS AtoN is a specific type of AIS used to enhance maritime navigation. AIS AtoN devices are installed on navigation aids, such as buoys, lighthouses, and beacons, to provide information about these aids to nearby vessels.

Glomex RA304 antenna

The Glomex RA 304 is a VHF antenna commonly used in AIS (Automatic Identification System) and radio communication systems on marine vessels.

Such antenna provides good signal quality and range, which are crucial for effective communication and AIS operation. Other important feature is its small size, the antenna is relatively compact, making it easy to install on small vessels. Made from durable, corrosion-resistant materials, which is essential for marine environments.

Tallysman GPS L1 Patch Antenna 1.575GHZ, 39DB

It is a permanent mount GPS L1 antenna, specially designed for professional precision timing applications. The TW3040/TW3042 features a custom high performance, wide band patch element, a 40dB gain LNA stage and a high rejection out-of-band SAW filter. The TW3042 is equipped with a sharp SAW pre-filter to

provide strong protection from out-of-band signals. It provides ± 10 MHz bandwidth centred on 1575.42 MHz and covers the GPS L1, Galileo E1 and SBAS (WAAS/EGNOS/MSAS) signals, and it provides great axial ratio, excellent circular polarized signal reception, great multipath rejection and great out-of-band signal rejection.

easyRX3 receiver (buoy)

The easyRX3 is a device that is part of the AIS. It is an AIS receiver designed to receive AIS signals from other vessels.

Glomex RA111AIS antenna:

The Glomex RA111AIS antenna is a popular choice among sailors and ship operators for its reliability, durability, and performance, helping to enhance maritime safety through effective communication and maritime traffic monitoring.

The RA111AIS is specifically designed for optimal AIS signal reception and transmission, ensuring effective vessel communication and monitoring. Its construction, using durable, corrosion-resistant materials, guarantees long-term reliability in harsh marine environments. The compact design allows for easy installation on various vessels, while the wide frequency range supports both AIS and VHF communications.

Nomad2 Portable Class B AIS Transponder (vessel)

The Nomad2 Class B AIS Transponder is a portable device that allows for the transmission and reception of AIS signals, ensuring other vessels can see your position and other important navigational data. It can be powered via a USB port, making it easy to connect to various power sources, such as power banks, laptops, or the boat's electrical system. It comes with a compact VHF and GPS antenna combination.

Figure 19 *The Nomad2 Portable Class B AIS Transponder*

Source: L-PIT own study

The integration of intelligent river buoys, bridge sensors, and vessel transmitters represents a highly innovative process requiring robust engineering and creativity. This endeavor aimed to seamlessly unite specialized components into a system designed to revolutionize the monitoring and management of shipping routes.

The system integrates intelligent river buoys equipped to gather critical data, that communicate wirelessly with bridge sensors and vessel transmitters, enabling real-time gathering and transmission of comprehensive route conditions.

Key to the integration was the utilization of AIS/ATON NMEA standard communication for inland navigation compliance, ensuring seamless data exchange between all system components. Moreover, the system's ability to autonomously communicate with vessels moving along the route provides invaluable data on transport timeliness, potential delays, and operational efficiencies. This real-time information empowers dynamic traffic management and optimizes operations at transshipment ports.

In conclusion, the integration process not only involved technical refinement but also addressed the complex logistical challenges of real-time data aggregation and interpretation. It marks a significant advancement in maritime technology, poised to elevate efficiency and safety across inland waterways.

Buoys and clearance sensors location

All elements of the system will be installed along pilot site on Vistula river, according to recommendations received from barge operator. The idea of the location was to put the devices at the key milestones of the voyage and potential bottlenecks. Below table shows exact GPS position for each element of the system.

Table 19 GPS position for each system component

Object	Type	GPS
Bridge clearance sensor - Gdansk	Clearance sensor	54.35507, 18.67718
Smart Buoy - Przegalina Lock	Smart Buoy	54.30731, 18.93343
Bridge clearance sensor - Kiezmark	Clearance sensor	54.25701, 18.9453
Smart Buoy - Grudziadz	Smart Buoy	53.48432, 18.74093
Smart Buoy – Bydgoszcz Fordon	Smart Buoy	53.14391, 18.17328
Smart Buoy - Torun	Smart Buoy	53.00334, 18.59425
Smart Buoy – Wloclawek Quay	Smart Buoy	52.72102, 18.98946

Source: Own Elaboration

6.4. Stakeholders

The organization of inland waterway voyage necessitates the involvement of multiple entities, each constituting a distinct link in the transport chain. The coordination of activities among these entities is the responsibility of the third-party logistics operator (3PL). This central entity decides on the necessity of engaging specific subcontractors, coordinates the flow of information, and ensures the efficient functioning of the entire supply chain. Below scheme shows the relationships and data exchange process between all stakeholders.

Figure 20 Stakeholders scheme

Source: L-PIT own study

Logistics Operator (3PL)

Through a tender announced by the project leader, the company Van Cargo, headquartered in Warsaw, will execute the trial cruises according to a specification requested by consortium. As a logistics operator, the company specializes in building and coordinating transport chains across all modes of transportation. For the Cristal project pilots, Van Cargo will be responsible for the comprehensive execution of the cruises. Van Cargo, as a third-party logistics (3PL) operator has its' expertise in developing comprehensive supply chains. The company gathered the experience in building inland waterway transport (IWT) solutions, leveraging its extensive experience to optimize multimodal logistics. Van Cargo excels in coordinating complex transport chains. Company in the framework of cristal voyages will collaborate with appropriate entities necessary for the efficient execution of transport within the designated supply chains. Collaborating entities include:

Inland Barge Operator

The operator of the barge, or the inland carrier indicated by VAN cargo is company Żegluga na Odrze, based in Stepnica. The company possesses a fleet of push-tug and barge sets as well as motor barges, one of which will be deployed for the project cruises. The fleet of motor barges consist of four units with the

capacity from 749 tons up to 2189 tons. Zegluga na Odrze owns also three pushers and four barges with capacity from 475 up to 780 tons. The tasks of the shipping operator, besides executing the inland transport, also include liaising with the infrastructure manager to control the navigability of the planned waterway, ordering lock services, opening bridges, and settling the costs of access to inland infrastructure.

Cargo Owners / Shippers

Depending on the type of cargo selected for the respective voyages, three shippers should be identified as stakeholders in the transport operations:

For cruises on the Vistula River with general and containerised cargo, the cargo owner, who is also the shipper, will be a chemical plant from Włocławek. The company produces fertilizers and a wide range of chemical products, as a member of state owned conglomerate. Company exports its products to overseas customers via the ports of Gdańsk and Gdynia, typically using road or rail transport. The weekly export transport volume in this supply chain is estimated on 3,0 thousand tons. Plant owns a quay along Vistula river unfortunately, it is not actively utilized in daily transport operations.

For voyages with bulk cargo, cargo owner indicated by operator is the company Polcopper, which deals in the purchase, segregation, and sale of steel scrap and non-ferrous metals. The cargo lot, designated for a Middle Eastern customer, will be dispatched from the quay in Płock to the seaport in Gdańsk, where it will be unloaded at Polcopper's own quay. Polcopper typically uses its own road fleet or rail transport for such shipments. The weekly volume of scrap handled by Polcopper in this supply chain is estimated at 1000 tons.

The international voyage via the Oder Waterway will be a part of the standard supply chain managed by VAN group. Goods which are usually transported by road, or rail will with usage of containers will be shifted on IWW solutions. As this transport chain is based on goods consolidation from variety of locations it is impossible to indicate exact shippers or cargo owners. Logistics operator usually transport FMCG, Furnitures and car spare parts westbound. As a backhaul cargo operator pickup raw materials from Anwerp chemical and steel plants to Polish production facilities.

Technology Providers

During the cruise on the Vistula River, smart buoy technology supporting supply chain transparency will be tested. The technology, developed within the project, will be supplied by Lukaszewicz – Poznan Institute of Technology. As the first beneficiary of this technology, the pilot operator will receive an interface connection from L-PIT for monitoring barge movement and estimating arrival times.

Terminals and quays

One of the responsibilities of the voyage operator is to identify optimal handling facilities for selected commodities and supply chains. Desk research clearly indicated a limited availability of infrastructure for inland waterway cargo handling. Additionally, none of the available and active quays and terminal along the pilot routes on the Oder and Vistula rivers are connected to a railway network, which would enable to perform efficient intermodal transportation and thus support synchromodal transport strategies. Furthermore, some quaysides are not directly linked to road infrastructure such as expressways,

motorways, or national road networks. These infrastructural limitations contribute to a reduced inclination among cargo owners to shift their volumes to inland water transport

The designated destination port for the Vistula River voyages is the seaport of Gdańsk. Two quays will be utilized for cargo handling within the port. Containerized cargo, depending on quay and oceangoing vessels availability availability may be delivered directly on Baltic Hub – container terminal located on external aquatory of Gdansk Port. Baltic Hub handle approx 2,0mln TEU annually, and plays a significant role on Baltic containerised seafreight market. In case of quay unavailability, containers may be handled at the quay managed by Port Gdańsk Eksploatacja (PGE). PGE is one of many quay operators at the port of Gdańsk, managing five quays and handling approximately 6.9 million tons of cargo annually, ranging from bulk to conventional general cargo and ro-ro cargo.

General cargo – big bags will be delivered to quay administrated by company Fosfory. Terminal handles general unitised cargo, bulk and liquids on their daily operations, also for mentioned cargo, which is usually transported by rail from facility to port of Gdansk.

Bulk cargo will be handled at the quay managed by the aforementioned cargo owner. Polcooper operates on multi-use wharf with total length of 150m and offers cargo handling services for own cargo and for external partners.

Loading location for General cargo and containers on Vistula waterway was naturally indicated by cargo owner. Chemical plant administrates own quay on Vistula waterway, which is currently not in operations.

Plant quay in Wloclawek offers approximately 30m of wharf for barge mooring. Available length depends on current water level, as the wharf is closed by ro-ro slip. Additionally, concrete paved zone of 2000sqm allows to proceed reloading operations and arrange required by safety – reloading zone, cargo storage zone and road traffic zone. Location is connected with production plant by internal, asphalt road.

Figure 21 Quay at Wloclawek Plant

Source: Van Cargo own study

Due to limited availability of loading machinery at quay in Wloclawek it will be necessary to employ an external company providing crane services and using mobile loading equipment. The selection of the

appropriate equipment and subcontractor also falls under the responsibilities of the voyage operator. For the established chain, crane service will be provided by the company eM-Tech from Toruń.

Loading location for bulk cargo (metal scrap) has been indicated in Plock inland waterway port. Nowadays Plock inland port functions as a marina for tourist navigation and as an operational base for the infrastructure manager. It is also the location of the former inland navigation shipyard. Unfortunately, all permanent transshipment operations in Plock have been ceased. Currently, however, the quay allows for the safe storage of cargo intended for transshipment onto barges and its subsequent loading using mobile transshipment equipment.

Port Koźle, located at the mouth of the Gliwice Canal, covers an area of 22.50 hectares, with 11.30 hectares dedicated to three port basins. It has 3,185 meters of loading quays and 635 meters of mooring and other quays. The quays are designed for high-water levels, although all the loading equipment has been dismantled. Previously, the port's capacity was about 1 million tons annually. Currently, it can temporarily store up to 300,000 tons of materials, primarily coal. The port also includes a grain elevator with a capacity of 10,000 tons and storage yards covering 48,130 m². Despite efforts to establish a logistics center integrating water, road, and rail transport, these initiatives have yet not to succeed. Based on such status quo, operator is obliged to subcontract proper reloading equipment, such as cranes or reachstacker to secure optimal reloading process. Due to early stage of voyage setup, company involved in reloading operation is yet not chosen.

6.5. Schedule

Due to fluctuations in water levels and the execution of pilot cruises under real-world transport chain conditions, it is not possible to precisely determine the schedule of pilot cruises well in advance. Nevertheless, the operator of these cruises has provided a preliminary plan for the execution of transports.

Pilot I – General cargo

Wloclawek – Gdansk Fosfory Terminal – CW 41. 7-10/10/2024

Pilot II – Containers

Gdansk-Wloclawek-Gdansk – CW 47. 18-1/11/2024

Pilot III – Metal Scrap

Plock – Gdansk Polcopper terminal – CW40. 1-4/10/2024

Pilot IV – Containers on international waterway incl. Oder river

Kozle – Antwerp – Kozle CW 42-43 14-25/10/2024

6.6. Alternative solutions

Analyzing the market for alternative transport solutions for inland waterway transport (IWT), especially in selected chains as a model for the Polish pilot, attention should be focused on solutions previously employed by the chosen logistics operator. In practice, the selected IWT chains currently operate primarily on road or rail transport. Unfortunately, the limited availability of infrastructure and intermodal points for IWT across various transport sectors precludes the implementation of synchromodal strategies. However, alternative transport methods can successfully be applied, particularly for bulk cargo. Standard practice in the existing supply chain involves road transport between the purchasing and sorting facility and the terminal at the port of Gdańsk.

Anwil's supply chain is predominantly based on rail transport, constituting 90% of transport between its industrial siding in Włocławek and the seaport in Gdańsk or alternatively Gdynia. This involves utilizing block train shipments. For containerized cargo smaller than full train loads, Anwil leverages intermodal transport via the available network of rail container terminals. The nearest intermodal terminal to Włocławek, located in Kutno, facilitates daily operator-run connections such as PCC Intermodal to the ports of the Tricity area. The proximity of Kutno, approximately 60 km from Włocławek, also allows for increased total mass of road train sets, which positively impacts the economic feasibility of such solutions. The remaining 10% of Anwil's transports are conventional road transports, using articulated container trucks or direct delivery to the ports of the Tricity.

Below is a table presenting the options and estimated unit transport costs and transit times:

Table 20 *Alternative routings for Pilot voyages*

Pilot	Alternative I	Routing	Estimated unit cost	Estimated transit time
I General cargo	Block train	Terminal Fosfory - Gdansk Zaspas Station – Wloclawek Station – Plant Wloclawek	9EUR/t	10h
II Containers	Block Train	Baltic Hub- Gdansk Port Port Polnocny – Wloclawek – Plant Wloclawek	300EUR/TEU	9h
III Bulk	Block Train	Plock Station-Gdansk Port Polnocny – Polcopper Terminal Gdansk	12EUR/t	12h

IV Containers Oder	Intermodal shuttle	Gliwice PCC – Antwerp CombinANT	1200EUR/TEU	27h
Pilot	Alternative II	Routing	Estimate	Estimated transit time
I General cargo	Road transport door-door	Fosfory terminal-Plant Wloclawek	12EUR/t	6h
II Containers	Slot at regular intermodal shuttle	Plant-Kutno-Terminal – Baltic Hub terminal	700EUR/TEU	9h
III Bulk	Road transport door-door	Plock area – Polcopper Terminal Gdansk	18EUR/t	8h
IV Containers Oder	Road transport door-door	Gliwice area – Antwerp area	1800EUR/TEU	18h

Source: Own elaboration

6.7. Key Performance Indicators and baseline

The effectiveness and outcomes of the conducted pilots will be measured through efficiency indicators developed by the Cristal consortium within WP 6.1. These indicators are categorized into three areas: economic, environmental, and social aspects. Each indicator has its own calculation methodology and refers to specific supply chains. To accurately assess changes after the implementation of IWT (Inland Waterway Transport) into the transport chain, cargo owners with pilot operator have estimated baseline values for efficiency indicators.

Economic

E5-Tracked vs total shipments

Indicator compares number of cargo units (containers or tons) under GPS surveillance with all units transported in indicated period of time. For selected supply chains, logistics operator measure and compare the KPIs on weekly basis. Indicator will show, if introducing IWW will improve supply chain visibility for cargo owners and operators.

$$E_5 = \frac{V_m}{V_t} * 100\%$$

Where:

V_m = Cargo volume monitored (in tons, or TEU)

V_t = Cargo volume freighted weekly in supply chain (in tons, or TEU)

General cargo

Supply chain for general cargo currently operates on rail transport between plant in Wloclawek and terminals in Gdansk Port. Rail operator who's providing the service has 100% of locomotives equipped in GPS transponders, so all of the goods are 100% monitored.

Bulk cargo

Scrap loadings are exclusively transported by shipper's own trucks fleet, which 100% of them are equipped in GPS telematics system, so baseline for this supply chain has been set at 100%

Containerised cargo Vistula

Containerised cargo from Wloclawek plant is usually transported by road to Gdansk. Based on shippers knowledge, approx. 80% of the trucks deployed for this supply chain are equipped in GPS transponders.

Containerised cargo Oder

Fourth supply chain is based on railway shuttle between Gliwice and Antwerp with a supporting role of long distance road haulage. Thus 100% of units transported by rail are monitored, and approximately 80% of trucks are equipped in GPS telematics. It is estimated that current baseline for this parameter in mentioned supply chain is 90% of units are under GPS surveillance.

E6-Operational efficiency

Operational efficiency describes how many cargo units can be transported per single transportation process. It is expected, that IWW introduction will significantly improve the efficiency of logistics operation, previously performed with pure road transport, and may decrease in comparison to rail shuttles deployed within framework of current supply chains

$$E_6 = V_t$$

Where:

V_t = Cargo volume freighted per single transportation order (Tones or TEU)

General cargo

For general cargo, currently transported by rail, single transportation order contains 1500 tons of chemical products laden in bigbags, transported by rail in Ha type wagons.

Bulk Cargo

Metal scrap is transported in selected supply chain, solely by road. This means, that single shipment cannot exceed max. 40 tons incl truck. In practice, maximum 24 tons of scrap can be laden onto single tipper truck.

Containerised cargo Vistula

Supply chain with containerised cargo from Wloclawek plant on its baseline also works on railway traffic. Standard capacity of intermodal block train is considered as 88 TEU, so this under has to be set as baseline measurement for mentioned transportation chain.

Containerised cargo Oder

Slightly different chain configuration takes place on selected Chain on Oder river. Here 80% of units are transported by rail, and rest of the units are transported by road. As mentioned, standard intermodal block train in Poland has capacity of 88 TEU, whereas European standard truck can carry max 2 TEU. Weighted average on those two values provides the capacity per order 70 TEU as a baseline.

E7-Status updates

Frequency of shipment status updates significantly impacts the overall transparency and visibility of the supply chain. Regular updates on the current position and expected arrival at designated milestones enhance logistics planning, streamline terminal workflows, and improve last-mile scheduling, ultimately ensuring a smooth unloading process at the final destination and preventing congestion.

$$E_7 = Q_u$$

Where

Q_u = number of shipment status updates provided to shipper per hour.

General cargo

Rail company invoiced in current supply chain configuration updates the shipment status, only in case of disruptions and delays during the voyage, average number of updates do not exceed two for each 9 hour trip, which provides the baseline at level 0,22 updates per hour.

Bulk cargo

Scrap shipments arranged currently by road, due to its non time sensitivity are not under any regular status updates. Trucks fleet managed by shipper are delivering the goods to the quay in Gdansk once per day, providing only one update at the end of the workday, which provides the baseline at the level 0,1 update / hour.

Containerised cargo Vistula and Oder

Containerised units are currently freighted only or mainly by rail on both pilots with similar density of status updates as per general cargo – 0,2 update per hour.

E8-Actual vs planned shipments

Implementation of Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) into supply chains may impact the expected weekly capacity. Therefore, a KPI measuring the supply chain's responsiveness to shippers' demand has been developed. Comparing the scheduled volume versus the actual volume transported, measured as a percentage, allows for assessing whether the newly developed supply chain is more flexible than previously used solutions. On the other hand, the share of actual shipments may vary from planned from the reasons not related to transport chain, and can remain related to sales contracts, production schedules or product quality.

E9-Delays/Waiting times

One of measured indicators describing supply chains is the punctuality of service. Thus, pilot includes comparison of estimated voyage schedules with actual barge schedules. The difference between those values will give the real deviations and reliability of service.

$$E_9 = ta_a - ta_e$$

Where:

t_{a_a} = actual arrival time

t_{a_e} = estimated arrival time

General Cargo, Containerised cargo

Cargo owner do not measure the delays for rail freight transport in the supply chains. Although, average delay of the freight train in Poland is estimated on 780minutes, which was indicated as baseline measurement of delay in current supply chain configuration.

Bulk goods

Scrap metal transported by road in tipper trailers are subject to delays caused mainly by road accidents or weather conditions. Unfortunately, shipper do not measure the average delay time for their trucks fleet, although they estimated 4 hours as an average delay time.

E12-Operational cost of a fixed route

Economic efficiency of supply chain per transported unit gives a natural foundations to develop and implement IWT into further supply chains. Thus, pilots will provide real costs of transportation per cargo unit with implemented IWW solutions.

$$E_{12} = \frac{C_t}{V_t}$$

Where:

C_t = total costs of transportation

V_t = volume transported (tons or teu)

General cargo

Currently, estimated costs of railway transportation from plant Wloclawek to Gdansk port is 36PLN/ ton of cargo, depending on exact batch quantity and number of trains contracted.

Containerised cargo

For rail transport of containers costs calculation has to be conducted based on a round trip voyage with empty containers delivered from the depots located in seaports. Thus, the baseline cost per TEU is set on 1250PLN/TEU for Vistula and 1250EUR/TEU for Oder – Antwerp voyage.

Bulk cargo

Scrap steel selected as a model cargo for pilot voyage is transported by tipper trucks from collection facilities nearby Plock city area to Gdansk terminal facility managed by shipper. Trucks are also owned by

shipper, thus transport cost rate 9EUR/t indicated by shipper may vary from rates offered on transportation market by freight forwarders or road hauliers.

E13-Overall corridor transit time (minutes/km)

Another critical factor influencing the success of Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) in real supply chains is total transit time. Generally, the market refers to the baseline transit time experienced daily. When integrating IWT into supply chains, it is essential to ensure that transit times are not significantly extended while achieving tangible economic or environmental benefits.

$$E_{13} = \frac{t_{iww} + t_{ro} + t_h + t_{ra}}{S_t}$$

Where:

t_{iww} = total transit time by IWW voyage

t_{ro} = total transit time by road

t_h = total time spent on handling between transport means

t_{ra} = total transit time by rail

S_t = total distance

Pilot I, II General cargo and containers on Vistula

Baseline parameters are referring to currently used configuration chain. As per shipper declaration total transit time for delivery by rail from plant siding to terminal shall not exceed 540 minutes one way which means approximately 2,5min/km.

Pilot III Bulk cargo

Bulk metal scrap is currently transported by trucks owned by shipper. Although, shipper is not measuring trucks transit time per corridor. According to declaration, average speed of truck do not exceed 55km/h which can be considered as 1,1min/km

Pilot IV Containers on Oder

Van cargo, as the operator of supply chains between silesia region and Antwerp is using both road and intermodal solutions to get best performance depending on time sensitivity for each cargo. Considering intermodal road-rail as a leading solution, operator declared average transit time door-door 2,5day or 60hours. Thus, 3min/km has been set as baseline for this corridor.

UG-1 Tons transported / TEU transported weekly

Measuring total volume of goods transported on weekly basis allow to compare the transport capability between particular solutions. Currently, every pilot voyage has its baseline indicated by cargo owner. Baseline has been indicated on supply chain parameters including:

- Production capacity
- Transport capacity – incl. means of transportation and terminals throughput.
- Commercial needs (demand)

UG-2 Barge cargo capacity utilisation

The utilization of available cargo space on a barge impacts the unit transport cost and may therefore influence entrepreneurs' willingness to transform supply chains and implement inland navigation into their operations. This indicator is expressed as a percentage of the number of loaded compared to the available space on the barge. As IWW is currently not implemented in selected supply chains, baseline relates to estimated barge utilisation during performed pilots and will be compared with actual utilisation after performing pilot voyages.

$$UG_2 = \frac{V_t}{V_v} * 100\%$$

Where:

V_t = total transported volume (tons or TEU)

V_v = vessel capacity (tons or TEU)

General cargo:

Shipper estimates to load approximately 750 tons of products in big bags laden in three layers in barge holds. This will allow to 100% utilize the vessel

UG-3 IWW share in total supply chain distance

This indicator shows the percentage share of inland waterway transport in the entire supply chain in terms of distance covered. Based on this, it will be possible to determine the final distances of the last mile completed by barges, and assess the need for expanding the appropriate terminal-port infrastructure network. As mentioned before, currently any of indicated supply chains use IWW transport, thus the baseline for all pilot voyages equals 0%

$$UG_3 = \frac{S_{IWW}}{S_T} * 100\%$$

Where

S_{IWW} = Distance performed by inland waterways

S_T = Total distance performed in transport chain

UG4 - Total manhours of staff involved in supply chain

The implementation of an inland waterway-based supply chain requires the involvement of a team to develop the supply chain and subsequently work on its implementation, supervision, and coordination of daily operational activities. To assess the workload involved in establishing and executing the transport chain, logistics operator's staff worktime will be measured in terms of effort put into the inland waterway transport.

$$UG_4 = t_{vp} + t_{vo}$$

Where:

t_{vp} = manhours required for concept work

t_{vo} = manhours required for operational work (including backoffice and directly involved staff)

Environmental

ENV1-Share of freight transport on IWT

This environmental indicator measures the share of inland waterway intermodal transport within all modes used in a specific supply chain over a defined period of time. For supply chains managed by the selected logistics operator awarded through a tender process, selected reporting time unit is one week. Baseline for all supply chains involved in pilot equals zero, as currently none of them have implemented IWW transport.

$$ENV_1 = \frac{V_{IWW}}{V_T} * 100\%$$

Where:

V_{IWW} = Cargo volume transported by inland waterways

V_T = Total volume transported in supply chain

ENV4-NOX / ENV5-PM / ENV6-GHG as CO₂e / ENV7-Energy consumption per tonne kilometer

Naturally, when measuring the environmental impact of inland waterway transport, emissions cannot be overlooked. Therefore, among the indicators, nitrogen oxides, particulate matter, carbon dioxide emissions and consumed energy have been included. The emissions of the supply chain are calculated using the EcoTransIT tool (<https://www.ecotransit.org/>) both, for baseline parameters and for KPI's measuring outcome of implementation IWW into supply chains. All the emissions are calculated per tonekm or per transported tone for easier comparison of effects.

Social

Constructing efficiency indicators in social areas seems to be a significant challenge, as initial research and interviews reveal that public awareness of inland navigation remains low. The social indicators have been developed based on available statistical data and declarations from stakeholders involved in the project.

S2-Accidents along the transport network

The number of accidents indicated as the baseline corresponds to the annual scale of accidents in the transport network of the leading transport mode for each pilot voyage. For voyages I, II, and IV, the baseline indicator will be rail transport, while for the transport of steel scrap, the baseline will be road transport and the annual number of road accidents.

S3- Time to react

According to declarations from the infrastructure manager, due to the low level of traffic and the corresponding low number of accidents on the waterways, there are no established procedures for measuring the reaction time to accidents. Consequently, the baseline for this indicator is set at level 0.

S4-Availability of multimodal transport information

The indicator of multimodal transport service availability will be assessed precisely after the voyages, particularly during the living lab included in WP7 and the socio-economic studies conducted widely within WP9. However, even before these activities, stakeholders and market observers can gauge the perceived availability of multimodal transport services in Poland on a scale from 1 (no information or impossible) to 5 (excellent availability). Baseline, according to the shipper's declarations are set for all pilots at level 2 – minor information.

- 1 – no information
- 2 – minor
- 3 – Quite good
- 4 – good
- 5 – excellent

S5 Social acceptance

Social acceptance of developing IWW on baseline has been measured based on pilot's stakeholders involved in all the voyages.

- 1 – strongly disagree
- 2 – disagree
- 3 – neutral
- 4 – agree
- 5 – strongly agree

Baseline Values for all KPI as a basis for further evaluation during the pilot voyages has been provided below.

Table 21 KPI baseline level for particular voyages in polish pilot

KPI	Voyage I Containerised cargo Baseline or estimation	Voyage II General Cargo Baseline or estimation	Voyage III Bulk Cargo Baseline or estimation	Voyage IV Intl containerised cargo Baseline or estimation
Economic				
E5-Tracked vs total shipments (% /week)	80%	100%	100%	90%
E6-Operational efficiency (tonnes/TEU per shipment)	88 TEU	1500t	24t	70 TEU
E7-Status updates (updates/hour)	0,2	0,22	0,11	0,2
E8-Actual vs planned shipments		750t	500t	
E9-Delays/Waiting times (min)	780	780	240	780
E12-Operational cost of a fixed route (euro/cargo unit)	300EUR/TEU	9EUR/t	18EUR/t	1250EUR/TEU
E13-Overall corridor transit time (minutes/km)	2,5min/km	2,5min/km	1,1min/km	3min/km
UG-1 Tons transported TEU transported	80 TEU	3000 tons	1000 tons	40 TEU
<u>UG-2 Barge cargo capacity utilisation [% of barge capacity]</u>	100%	100%	100%	100%
UG-3 IWW share in total supply chain distance	0%	0%	0%	0%
UG4 - Total manhours of staff involved in supply chain per week	840	840	660	950

Environmental				
ENV1-Share of freight transport on IWT (% of total cargo in supply chain)	0%	0%	0%	0%
ENV4-NOX kg/tons transported	0,01kg/ton	0,01kg/ton	0,02kg/ton	0,015kg/ton
ENV5-PM10 kg/tons transported	0,06kg/ton	0,014kg/ton	0,02kg/ton	0,02kg/ton
ENV6-GHG as CO2e (tonnes of CO2e / tkm)	0,02 kg/tkm	0,02kg/tkm	0,05kg/tkm	0,03/tkm
ENV7-Energy consumption per tonne kilometre (MJ /tkm)	0,39 MJ/tkm	0,27 MJ/tkm	0,97 MJ/tkm	0,4MJ/tkm
Social				
S2-Accidents along the transport network	644	644	644	20 900
S3 - Time to react (response time/ return time)	0	0	0	0
S4-Availability of multimodal transport information (Information publicly available - Likert scale)	2	2	2	2
S5-Social acceptance survey results (Likert scale)	4	4	4	4

Source: Own elaboration

7. Conclusions

The study addressed significant challenges and opportunities within the IWT sector. Infrastructural limitations, regulatory hurdles, and market acceptance issues were highlighted, alongside the potential for infrastructure enhancement and market growth. The need for increased social awareness and acceptance of IWT was emphasized, with social acceptance indicators developed based on statistical data and stakeholder input. Furthermore, a series of research gave the background to prepare a set of tools and recommendations to operators and authorities, including the concept and costs estimates on developing reloading multi-use terminals along international waterways.

Efficiency and further development of IWW market were critical focus areas, with baseline indicators established in alignment with current supply chain configuration. This approach facilitated a comparative analysis of safety and efficiency, particularly in rail and road transport.

Strategic recommendations included targeted investments in infrastructure, regulatory reforms, and awareness campaigns to bolster the role of IWT in the transport sector. The study concluded by highlighting IWT's potential to significantly improve Poland's logistics and supply chain ecosystem, contributing to both economic growth and environmental sustainability.

The next step in the project, will be the implementation of pilot transports as a basis for verifying the assumptions made in this study. The pilot transports will also allow verification of the potential for the development of inland shipping and its implementation into multimodal transport chains. The cruises will also be the basis for an in-depth socio-economic study and the collection of feedback from project stakeholders.

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9. Appendices

<https://www.google.com/maps/d/edit?hl=pl&mid=1HWBI9vI0aHvKllqKpy3dSoffzRpGbGY&ll=53.20607219791357%2C18.67701344914541&z=8> – Pilot voyages map

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